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T3.2 MIDTVEST REGIONAL REPORT

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Authors: Lina Le Pelley, Teun Strikkers, George Xydis

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Author names and affiliations	Lina Le Pelley, Dutch Research Institute for Transitions, DRIFT Teun Strikkers, Dutch Research Institute for Transitions, DRIFT George Xydis, Aarhus Universitet, AU
Reviewer names and affiliations	Flávio Oliveira, FC.ID
Description	A review of the development of wind energy governance of repowering in MidtVest, Denmark. Specific attention is paid to distributive and procedural justice and how this is enacted in current governance practices in MidtVest, Denmark

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1. DISCLAIMER AND FOREWORD

This case study about wind energy developments in Midtvest, Denmark has been produced for the Horizon Europe JustWind4All (JW4A) project as part of WP3 task 3.2. The task aims to develop an understanding of regional challenges and opportunities around wind energy governance over the past 5-10 years to formulate key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is based on a mixed method approach including for each region: document reviews (around 50), 5-10 interviews with wind energy governance actors and a media and policy analysis. A comparative analysis across cases and across the project's regions allows for a better understanding of challenges and opportunities around effective and just wind energy governance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 COUNTRY CONTEXT

Denmark has been a pioneer of renewable energy, specifically wind energy, and has taken on an “expert role” in this sector since the 1990s. The ideal of self-sufficiency is incredibly important for Danish energy policy. Today, Denmark continues to be a large producer of wind energy, also exporting green technologies to other countries and wind energy to Germany (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 602). Denmark’s **energy mix** is dominated by renewables, which constitute 50% of energy production (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 599) but oil still holds an important role (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 600). Biomass accounts for some energy production, but given that 43% is imported and that the CO2 emissions from its production are only registered in the country of origin, its status as a sustainable energy source is disputed (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 601). Other energy sources like coal have become relatively unimportant, and there are plans to discontinue production.

Evolution of Denmark’s Electricity Mix 1990-2019

Source: IEA Data.

Figure 1: Evolution of Denmark’s Electricity Mix 1990-2019 (Menu, 2021)

In terms of objectives, **climate change** has become an increasing concern amongst the electorate and therefore an important policy factor for energy production. Already in the 90s, attempts were made to streamline addressing climate change; this was done by sector and policy integration through combining “climate” and “energy” into one ministry (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 614). In 2011, Denmark committed to reaching a zero-carbon economy by 2050 (International Energy Agency, 2021); and in the Climate Policy Plan of 2013, they committed to phasing out fossil fuels completely by 2030 and becoming 100% powered by renewable energy by 2035 (The Ministry of Climate, Energy and Building, 2013).

One of the main targets that Denmark is working towards today stems from the Danish Climate Act of 18 June 2020, which stipulates that Denmark should reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 70% in 2030 compared to the level in 1990 (Danish Energy Agency, 2022). In response to these ambitious goals, ministers of the Danish government have pushed a “**hockey stick**” approach: this scheme would involve waiting to implement renewable technologies until just before the deadline in 2030, with the hope that the technologies have become cheaper by this point in time. However, many actors believe the strategy will hinder

rather than help achieve the climate goals, as well as damage Denmark's position as a frontrunner in renewable energy (Bahn, 2020).

Denmark's strategy for deploying energy at this critical time involves a complex governance system. One of the **main actors** with decision making power in the energy sector is the Danish state, represented through the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities, which "sets the political direction for the energy sector" (Dyrhauge, 2022, pp. 602-603). This mainly involves collaborating extensively with its institutions (which include the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS), the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), the Danish Agency for Data Supply and Efficiency, and the Danish Energy Agency (DEA), amongst others) to ensure that Denmark reaches its target of a 70% reduction in greenhouse gases by 2030, as discussed above.

Under the Ministry, the Danish Energy Agency (DEA) is the main institute overseeing, regulating, and coordinating climate and energy programmes, as well as related policies, often by working together with municipalities and other important actors. The DEA is also generally responsible for issuing permits for offshore wind projects and determining energy governance. Energinet, an independent public enterprise also under the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities, manages electricity and gas grid infrastructure as Denmark's transmission system operator (TSO) (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 603). Both the DEA and Energinet operate separately from the Ministry, but under its jurisdiction.

Under Denmark's **decentralised** energy infrastructure system (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 605), and since the Local Government Reform of 2007, Denmark's 98 **municipalities** have also played a key role in decision-making for initiatives like onshore wind projects; where they select sites for wind energy, directly approve the new construction or repowering of wind turbines, and oversee local planning procedures (Sperling et al., 2009, p. 4). Onshore wind power planning and decision-making are heavily influenced by local governments, while offshore wind energy remains managed by the Danish government, with the Ministry of Climate, Energy, and Utilities in charge of keeping things on track. Government and parliamentary changes have also influenced wind energy development in the past: the governments of Fogh Rasmussen I (2001 - 2005) and later Løkke Rasmussen II (2005 - 2007) have terminated and delayed wind park investment (respectively). This demonstrates that some centralised support for wind energy is dependent on political factors, but a "bottom-up" approach elsewhere ensures that individuals, municipalities, or private companies can apply to local municipalities to develop onshore wind projects (Dyrhauge, 2022, pp. 608-609).

Local energy producers are also important actors, like Vestas, which has become "synonymous" with developing and supplying Danish wind energy (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 602); and Ørsted, Denmark's largest energy producer, which was controversially privatised by the government in 2014 (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 596). Foreign multinationals like the Swedish Vattenfall play a large role in the Danish energy sector, by developing power generating facilities like wind parks; and increased international influence and collaboration on new policies has had an impact as well. For example, since the Russian invasion of Ukraine, Denmark has entered into an energy agreement with fellow Baltic Sea countries Poland, Sweden, Germany, and Finland, to collaboratively and massively increase electricity production from offshore wind as a strategy to forgo buying Russian gas (Schuldt, 2022). Denmark is also involved in the European Commission project "REPowerEU", which was initiated for the same reasons and which mobilises 300 million for investing into the green

transition (Færch, 2022).

EU policies and influence have also significantly impacted the Danish energy sector. A recent example is the Council Regulation 2022/2577 on a framework for accelerating the deployment of renewable energy, which the EU adopted on 22 December 2022 (Council of the European Union, 2022). This regulation aims to shorten the time taken to approve renewable energy implementation: it stipulates, amongst other points, that the permit-granting process for repowering renewable energy projects should not exceed 6 months, and shortens this period to 3 months if the repowering initiative will increase energy capacity up to 15%. This EU regulation had immediate effect in Danish law and took precedence over Danish regulations, in support of renewable energy as a vital societal interest.

On the other hand, the Danish government recently suspended the “**open door**” scheme for offshore wind development, due to a newly created Marine Plan for renewable energy, and because of doubts that the scheme aligned with EU regulations (Durakovic, 2023). The “open door” procedure allowed offshore wind developers to apply to develop wind farms “on their own initiative”, granting them flexibility in choosing a location and defining the scope of the project. Many argue that the procedure allowed for “more cost-competitive projects and more efficient site selection” (WindEurope, 2023) and that its suspension is detrimental to the needed acceleration of renewable energy, as most offshore wind projects have since been halted or rejected. Recent actions like this have generated considerable scepticism about whether wind energy can still be expanded to the extent it would need to be in order to meet Denmark’s climate goals.

Specifically for wind energy, despite having roots in bottom-up participation through **wind cooperatives** (which were originally formed by local initiative groups), today’s electricity sector has undergone **market liberalisation**, and now large companies take precedence as they have the most funds available to invest in increasingly expensive wind energy projects (especially offshore wind energy, which many perceive as the way forward for Danish wind) (Möller, 2010, p. 235; Kirkegaard et al., 2023, p. 657). The cooperative ownership model originally emerged in the 1980s with the growth of wind power in Denmark. Arguably, this **ownership system** helped wind energy garner public support and become a successful technology in the first place (Sperling et al., 2009). By definition, cooperatives have a democratic decision-making and open membership process, and all local residents of an area are invited to partake in the ownership of wind turbines near them, and are guaranteed involvement in planning and decision making from the very beginning (Gorroño-Albizu et al., 2019, p. 6). Cooperatives in the traditional sense still exist in Denmark, but there has been an increase in individual ownership, alongside other, newer forms of collective ownership, which are often on a national rather than local scale. **Wind guilds**, for example, differ with a decision making process based on share ownership and a closed membership system, making them more of a commercial rather than community-based arrangement (Gorroño-Albizu et al., 2019, p. 7).

Given Denmark’s long wind development history as well as relatively high community ownership, it is interesting to explore how these two factors have developed. Large-scale initiatives needed significant investments, and it was difficult for communities to follow their pace: between 2000-2015, municipalities began to “outsource maintenance and development of the local energy grids to private actors” (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 603). In a broader sense, the scale and cost associated with wind energy development increased due

to increases in capacity, and coupled with the EU's requirement of public tendering (favouring larger scale projects at a lower cost) and a lack of economies of scale for smaller cooperatives when developing project sites, favours large utility scale wind developers over small-scale, locally-owned projects (Kirkegaard et al., 2023, p. 657). As a result, the landscape shifted from community-driven cooperatives to more market-oriented developments. Public opinions of onshore wind energy also changed, going from enthusiasm to scepticism, along with changes in policy and market factors. In certain municipalities, opposition to wind farms grew, while support for new onshore projects decreased. Offshore projects became the focus of Danish wind energy's future, in line with shifting public opinion.

Although local communities are still able to buy shares in wind energy projects, there are cases where large German wind corporations have bought up shares in Danish projects when local investors struggled to keep up, for example see (Kryger, 2018). Not only in terms of ownership, but actions related to Denmark's **export of wind energy** to Germany and other European countries have also caused some concern amongst local residents, despite originally representing "symbolic leadership" for Denmark (Dyrhauge, 2022, p. 602). For example, wind turbines are frequently turned off (despite high energy prices in Denmark) to prevent overloading the German grid, which is worrying for citizens (Bønke & Skov Andersen, 2022).

Repowering is also an important initiative, with the aim of increasing wind electricity production/capacity while utilising fewer turbines (Sperling et al., 2009, p. 8), which Denmark was one of the first countries to partake in on a large scale, with financial incentives supporting two major repowering initiatives from 1999 to 2003, and 2004 to 2010 (Gorroño-Albizu, 2018). Over the last two decades, Denmark's wind energy journey included issues of deteriorating wind turbines, changing support systems, fluctuating market dynamics, and shifting public opinion. In a period of limited onshore space and increasing resistance, repowering initiatives in combination with offshore wind have significantly contributed to the future of Danish wind energy.

1.2 REGIONAL CONTEXT

Business Region MidtVest (BRMV) is a collaboration between the seven Central and West Jutland municipalities Struer, Lemvig, Herning, Holstebro, Ikast-Brande, Skive and Ringkøbing-Skjern. The goal of the collaboration is to help develop the seven municipalities further and maintain a strong Central and West Jutland in the long term (Business Region MidtVest, 2023).

Figure 2: Municipalities of Business Region MidtVest (Manufacturing Festival Denmark, 2022)

Figure 3: Danish Business Regions - Region MidtVest pictured in brown (KL - Kommunernes Landsforening, 2016)

The advantageous geographical position of one of the municipalities (Ringkøbing-Skjern) of the Business Region MidtVest in relation to the Esbjerg port (a distance less than 50 km from the port) – foreseen as the world’s largest base port for offshore wind activities – means significant opportunities for the local wind industry. This means that because Esbjerg is a

major port city in Denmark, and given its strategic position on the west coast this location is essential because it provides easy access to offshore wind farms in the North Sea, an area where most offshore activities happen. Despite the Esbjerg port being located just outside of the BRMV, it plays an important role due to its proximity to local wind industry actors in MidtVest, like local companies that are involved in the production, maintenance, and development of wind energy technologies, including a major OEM, subcontractors, and related infrastructure.

These businesses could range from wind turbine manufacturers to service providers, and they contribute significantly to the renewable energy sector. The municipalities' proximity to the Esbjerg port can bring about substantial benefits to the local wind industry. These benefits could include lower transportation costs for wind components, faster access to offshore wind farms for maintenance and construction, and the potential for increased economic activity and job creation in the region. To summarise, Esbjerg's importance for the future of offshore wind energy means that there is a lot of investment and development potential for local wind industry actors related to this area.

The total share of wind energy produced in the BRMV's seven municipalities is the largest contribution to Denmark's total production of wind energy in Denmark compared to the other business districts (Plan- og Landdistrikstyrelsen, 2023). This demonstrates that the MidtVest region is a prime location for wind energy, and therefore a highly significant area for investigating important factors like procedural and distributive justice, local involvement, and the roles of different actors in the Danish wind energy sector.

Beyond the wind industry, a diverse range of companies, both large international corporations and small to medium-sized enterprises, operate across various industries in the BRMV. The business landscape in Central and West Jutland has continually adapted to changing conditions, and this mindset and collaborative strength within the business region are vital for ensuring continuous development. It is essential to create a conducive environment for businesses to excel in their core activities, and in this sense, the BRMV serves as the focal point for weaving business development efforts under a common umbrella.

The strong relevance of offshore wind in this region, especially in terms of wind energy development in the near future, is interesting given that MidtVest also has a large number of onshore wind projects (which are approved and managed by the local municipalities). The large number of onshore wind turbines means that repowering initiatives have a lot of potential for significantly increasing energy capacity/production in the area and helping Denmark reach its climate/renewable energy targets; yet, repowering has declined in popularity and is largely absent from the planning for future wind energy production in the area. Many actors see the future of wind energy in offshore wind.

The region's focus on offshore wind projects (which are managed by government agencies like the DEA) is interesting given the high volume of onshore wind turbines and the region's strong potential for repowering programmes: why is this dynamic present/in place, and what factors are at play here? Why are there not more extensive plans for onshore repowering in MidtVest/why is offshore seen as the best option for the future? The status of MidtVest as a large producer of Danish wind energy, and the strong presence of both onshore and offshore initiatives, make it the ideal area/landscape for investigating these dynamics. Furthermore, MidtVest's status as a business region means that exploring and answering

these questions is important for all actors involved in and affected by the energy sector here, and supports the aim of the BRMV to increase its collaborative strength and develop the municipalities further.

1.2.1 REPOWERING

Compared to other countries in the EU, Denmark is at the forefront of wind energy development (Dyrhauge, 2017). This can be attributed to the vast early installation of wind turbines in the country, which stands in contrast with other EU countries. Having had an early start with wind energy deployment has meant that Denmark has to address ageing issues with wind turbines earlier (Fitzgerald & Giberson, 2021). In order to meet climate targets, Denmark had to implement various solutions, one of which was repowering (Kitzing et al., 2020).

Wind repowering in Denmark encounters challenges primarily in the realms of regulatory complexity, community engagement, and financial considerations. The intricate regulatory framework demands clear guidelines for navigating permits and environmental assessments, while fostering community consensus proves crucial concerns about visual impact and noise. Transitioning to a more community-centric ownership model requires careful governance adjustments and motivation - often financial incentives. Additionally, integrating advanced wind turbine technology, conducting thorough environmental impact assessments, and ensuring policy consistency are essential aspects that demand effective governance structures. Denmark's experience in addressing these challenges serves as a valuable reference for other regions aiming to transition to sustainable wind energy sources while fostering community involvement and navigating regulatory intricacies.

In Denmark, local communities often play a significant role in decision-making, and there is a strong emphasis on ensuring that the benefits of repowering projects extend to the people living in the vicinity. This community-centric approach is not as prevalent in some other regions where repowering efforts may be more centralised. Denmark's commitment to research and development in wind energy technology contributes to the innovation seen in its repowering projects. The country actively invests in cutting-edge solutions, making its repowering efforts not only about replacing outdated turbines but also about pushing the technological boundaries for increased efficiency and sustainability (Interview 1, 2023). In contrast to some regions where repowering may face challenges related to regulatory hurdles or community opposition, Denmark's proactive and inclusive approach sets it apart.

In this report, like in academic literature, repowering is defined as replacing part or the whole of the turbine and installing a new wind turbine for it. This does not have to be in the same exact location but could be in the vicinity of the old plant, however, exact definitions of "repowering" from country to country vary. The condition is that the new and old turbines should both be included in the development plan. However, the Danish definition is more specific. Section (§) 5, No. 28 of the Danish Electricity Supply Act (*Elforsyningsloven*) defines repowering as: "Renewal of electricity production facilities that produce renewable electricity, including full or partial replacement of facilities or operating systems and equipment with a view to replacing capacity or to increase the facility's productivity or capacity" (Retsinformation, 2021). The interpretation of this utilised by the Danish Energy Agency (DEA) and Danish Wind Turbine Valuation Authority (*Taksationsmyndigheden*)

furthermore states that, to be defined as repowering, “a project must [...] lead to the reuse of, for example, location, project components and infrastructure to an extent where it can be said that these are changes to an existing renewable energy plant and not a new construction project” (Energistyrelsen, n.d.). Essentially, this means that the official legal definition of the term in Denmark is that repowering requires the installation of new wind turbines in the exact locations of the old ones (email communication, October 6, 2023). However, some regional actors like those on a municipality level used our report’s definition of repowering (Interview 3, 2023).

Following our definition of repowering and the important role that repowering has in securing sustainable energy targets for Denmark (Pinson et al., 2017), in this report we are investigating the governance of repowering in Denmark. Specifically, we are focusing on onshore locations due to the involvement of inhabitants in the process. Consequently, we are investigating how procedural and distributive justice is taken into account across various municipalities in the MidtVest region when repowering wind turbines.

1.3 AIMS AND REPORT STRUCTURE

This case study traces the development of wind energy governance in the midwestern (MidtVest) region of Denmark, with a specific focus on repowering practices. It thus zooms in on how people participate in social actions and processes for or against wind energy, and outlines how these actions and processes are co-shaped by regulations, discourses, and norms over a certain period of time. Doing so allows us to highlight regional challenges and opportunities of wind energy governance. This report is one out of a set of seven case study reports that together will provide insights for the formulation of key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is in this way that it connects to JW4A’s ambition of understanding **how wind energy governance can become more just and effective**.

Specifically, this report provides an understanding of the interplay between diverse types of actors around wind repowering and energy governance in the MidtVest region. A brief historical overview or “pre-period” examines wind energy governance from 2000-2010 (Section 4.1). At the heart of this report is an overview of current repowering and governance practices in recent years, from 2010-2023 (now), and a comparison of three different wind turbine repowering projects in the MidtVest region (Section 4.3). The three projects were each based in a different municipality and consisted of the following: the Krejbjerg project in Skive Municipality, the Sdr. Bork Vindpark in Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, and the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines in Ikast-Brande Municipality. Each of these cases was analysed utilising the concepts of procedural and distributive justice, and selected to highlight the complex dynamics of wind repowering, energy governance, and participatory practices.

Central to our research are the following main research questions (RQs), see below. We answer these by first analysing past repowering governance practices. The current governance practices section aims to investigate the current repowering practices. The implications of the current practices are analysed next and address RQ 4, while the repowering case studies that follow dive deeper into RQ 1-3 by looking how distributive and procedural justice is enacted in practice. All these insights are discussed in the analysis and

discussion section in order to give a better understanding of all RQs. This serves the basis for the synthesis and recommendations.

Main Research Questions:

1. What role does distributive and procedural justice play in repowering in the MidVest region of Denmark?
2. To what extent does repowering in MidtVest enact distributive and/or procedural justice?
3. How has repowering affected the justice of wind energy development in the MidtVest region of Denmark?
4. What are the implications of (not) repowering on wind energy development in MidtVest?

The above main research questions serve as the base of our research. To further guide our research, we also aim to consider the following questions, which are part of the full case studies of T3.2.

- Which **governance arrangements and processes** are in place; that is, what was the ensemble of actors (human and non-human) that come together in the intentional coordination of social action around wind energy (for and against wind energy);
- Which **regulatory, normative and cultural-cognitive institutions** are co-shaping social activities around wind energy (these can derive from EU, national, regional and local, for instance, planning processes and landscape governance);
- Which **participatory practices** are being discussed and/or practised (or not) over time and how are they being perceived and implemented by diverse wind actors;
- And how are notions of **energy justice and energy sovereignty** being discussed, narrated, and practised (or not) over time? How do they relate to changing governance arrangements and processes?

Section 2 provides a succinct overview of the main insights of the analysis, while Section 6 provides implications and recommendations for fostering just and effective wind energy governance in the region and beyond. For an overview of the methodology underlying this report, please see Section 3.

2 KEY INSIGHTS

Repowering projects aiming to replace existing wind turbines in Denmark's MidtVest region are subject to permitting timeframes based on specific definitions, with faster approvals for projects conforming to the official definition. The municipality where the wind turbines are installed plays a pivotal role in determining whether a reduction in permitting time is applicable, possibly impacting the thoroughness of the process. If permitting times are to be reduced, careful consideration and transparency are important, given that the larger turbines installed through repowering often affect different groups of people, and more people in general.

Related to this, long permitting times and high costs often discourage local investors (Interview 1 and 2, 2023) from initiating their own repowering projects. The resulting high costs mean that many wind projects are managed or bought up by large companies (as in the case of the Krejbjerg project and the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines). Utilising new

or existing policy or subsidy programmes in this regard could make a difference, enabling communities to hold on to their wind projects and repower them themselves.

Current shortcomings: From the three selected case studies, it has become clear that even with systems in place that are focused on compensating residents (and arguably trying to ensure distributive justice), both public opposition and local involvement with wind repowering projects is complex and multifaceted. The existing policies in place to ensure distributive justice are not necessarily sufficient in terms of procedural justice. Currently, in repowering wind energy development procedural justice is mostly enacted through electing local officials and consultation meetings with the public. In these meetings it is unclear how big the role is of the citizens in influencing the process.

The role of public involvement: Considering the future of procedural justice, a key insight that emerged from all three case studies (and surrounding research) was that clarity and transparency are crucial factors in onshore repowering projects in Denmark, and wind energy development in general. It is vital to create an open dialogue between the municipality and citizens from the very beginning of the process, and access to information is an important part of this. In projects that lacked a collaborative, reciprocal planning process this was a point of contention.

Interestingly, wind energy project **developers** play an important role in how successful a wind project is by helping to facilitate the dialogue with local residents alongside, or often to a greater extent than, the municipality (interviewee 3). Local politicians often encourage developers to ensure that a wind project creates value for the local community: developers in Ringkøbing-Skjern receive a document with criteria they should adhere to and who they should engage with in the local community (Interview 3, 2023). The importance of local collaboration is also related to Denmark's history with **wind energy cooperatives**. This could help explain why people are often hostile towards developers who do not engage with the local population or who do not consider their perspectives when setting up wind/repowering projects.

Wind energy is "in our DNA": To some extent, it also seems that people feel a certain sense of personal obligation towards promoting wind energy and doing their part to combat the climate crisis. Interviewee 3 described that especially in this municipality, the city council and citizens alike believe that since they "have" the wind and the space, they have a certain responsibility to deliver with their wind projects. Not only was the large wind manufacturer Vestas founded in the municipality, but the Ringkøbing-Skjern's natural resources and history support the sentiment that "it's in [their] DNA" (Interview 3, 2023) to facilitate wind energy development. This might be connected to Denmark's history and international image as not only a frontrunner in wind energy, but renewable energy in general, relating back to the country's energy policies of the 1990s and schemes funding repowering.

The (visual) impact of wind turbines: Wind developments like the Sdr. Bork repowering project were also well-received because residents in the surrounding area were already used to wind turbines: the landscape around them already has wind turbines, so citizens are more receptive to turbines in general and to wind developments (Interview 3, 2023) - repowering cases where there is often a transition from many to fewer wind turbines are generally more popular. By definition, repowering is only done in areas where wind turbines already exist; this often helps to facilitate a positive public reception, or at least not an overtly negative one. Repowering projects do run into difficulties when the new turbines are significantly

larger than the old ones (even if there are fewer of them), as there is an increased visual impact which many residents do not appreciate.

The effect and role of current policies and legislation: The policies and procedures currently in place (like the buyer's rights scheme, the green pool, and the municipal planning/assessment process for onshore wind turbines) seem to insufficiently (or at least inconsistently) promote local ownership and involvement in repowering wind energy projects. This appears to be a factor that is still important for residents, and remains an issue despite initiatives like the buyer's rights scheme, which allows residents in the surrounding area to purchase shares in a wind energy project. To continue and encourage repowering practices, it is recommended that either existing policies are expanded to further boost local involvement, or that they are adapted. For example, facilitating more bottom-up than top-down decision making in the development process, or using the "green pool" as a point of investment for local residents so that they do not have to rely on relatively expensive shares.

Interviewee 3 described that it is also unclear for regional actors like the municipality to know when they have investigated "enough", when it comes to environmental assessments for wind projects. There are nationally determined guidelines and different authorities who provide insights for the report, but there is also EU legislation about protected nature areas and animal species: Interviewee 3 described that it is increasingly difficult to make these evaluations thorough enough, and that legislation is becoming "sharper" (Interview 3, 2023). This is significant because projects that do receive complaints claiming an insufficient environmental assessment are often delayed or cancelled entirely: complaints about species like birds or bats are especially powerful (Interview 3, 2023). As a result, there is pressure towards careful and thorough environmental assessments, as an insufficiency could mean the downfall of the project.

Furthermore, the **electricity surplus** generated by the majority of repowering projects has to be effectively accommodated; this is something that is not adequately addressed at the moment in every repowering project. A notable example is the Midtjyske Motorvej turbines, where due to grid limitations, the excess of produced electricity was not able to be used or transported. In light of increased grid restrictions, when repowering, it is important both in terms of public perception and renewable energy targets that the electricity has a possibility to be utilised.

Conclusion: These case studies highlight the complex interplay between procedural and distributive justice in wind energy governance, influenced by project definitions, community ownership, and compensation mechanisms. The involvement of municipalities and the evolving regulatory landscape impact the fairness and effectiveness of governance in wind energy projects.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

We carried out document reviews and interviews between September 2023 and December 2023. The process of finding relevant texts and articles involved using certain keywords like 'wind energy' 'wind park' 'repowering' 'governance' and 'Denmark' via platforms like Google

Scholar, Elsevier, and the Erasmus University Rotterdam library. Searching the websites of organisations and actors like the European Commission, the Danish Energy Agency (*Energistyrelsen/DEA*), and the Danish Wind Turbine Valuation Authority (*Taksationsmyndigheden*) generated useful information/documents related to governance and procedural explanations as well. This involved conducting some searches in Danish, in order to access more detailed information, using keywords like ‘vindmøller’, ‘repowering-projekter’, ‘vindenergi’, ‘vedvarende energi’, and ‘havvindmøller’.

Given that many of these sources were originally written in Danish, we used online platforms/services to translate them into English - this also involved cross-referencing translations from different services like Google Translate and DeepL, as well as various bilingual dictionaries, and cross-referencing different sources with one another to ascertain the accuracy/interpretation of the information being translated. Regardless of the origin of the different documents, we named and contextualised the source in the report to indicate its reliability.

The documents we reviewed included academic articles describing a general history of wind and renewable energy development in Denmark, governance and policies relating to this, as well as discussions/analyses of repowering initiatives, and comparisons of community-based versus liberalised/marketised wind power initiatives. Other documents included legal documents created by the EU/European Commission and policy documents related to EU renewable energy/repowering policies. We also examined Danish-language policy documents published by the Danish Energy Agency (DEA), the Ministry of Climate, Energy, and Utilities, as well as by individual municipalities.

We made extensive use of the database of the Danish Wind Turbine Valuation Authority (*Taksationsmyndigheden*), which contains documents detailing verdicts related to citizen compensation claims, and which we used to identify onshore repowering projects in the MidtVest region: this was possible because the summaries of the different wind projects on the database generally mentioned if older wind turbines were “taken down” or “decommissioned” in connection with a newly registered project. This process fits within our definition of “repowering”. Then, we assessed local municipality documents (detailing planning procedures, public hearings, consultation responses, and environmental reports) to gather information about individual repowering projects. Finally, we used Danish newspaper articles and online public forums to ascertain public opinion about the repowering projects and to gain knowledge from interviews that journalists conducted with stakeholders and actors involved.

We conducted three interviews in total. Two were with the wind turbine manufacturers Siemens Gamesa and a second Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) respectively, two of the largest corporations in this sector in Denmark (and with significant international influence). Our third interview was held with a representative of the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality about the planning process of the Sdr. Bork Vindpark repowering project. We conducted the interviews online and subsequently transcribed and summarised them. This process involved upholding certain regulations: for confidentiality purposes, the interview with Siemens Gamesa involved representatives from the corporation reviewing the transcription and notes from the interview before any part was added to the report, and to determine whether any anonymisation was necessary. The third interview allowed us to **triangulate** policy data we had obtained through our document review, and confirm our

understanding and interpretation of the Danish-language energy policies in effect within the case studies of this report.

3.2 EMPIRICAL REFLECTIONS

This case was investigated by a team of three researchers: a researcher/consultant (background in engineering side of energy transitions) and a research intern (background in anthropology and sociology) based in the Netherlands, and a senior researcher (background and experience in energy planning, wind resource assessment and energy policy) based in Denmark. The combination allowed us to benefit from the knowledge of the Danish wind energy sector held by the senior researcher, while maintaining some critical space from the subject matter through the more unfamiliar standpoint of the other two researchers. Our different academic backgrounds and experiences as researchers also allowed for interdisciplinarity (of perspectives and approaches), which aligns with the “transdisciplinary co-production work” at the core of JustWind4All’s research methodology.

Leading the research on the Danish case from the Netherlands without Danish language skills, meant that our initial research into the overall Danish energy context and repowering programmes in municipalities was largely based on academic texts written in English. Insights from academic articles were supplemented with two interviews in English with two different wind turbine/energy manufacturers, Siemens Gamesa and a second OEM, enquiring into perspectives and experiences within these large corporations in the Danish energy sector. There was no possibility to do participant observation for reasons of geographical distance, language barriers and restricted time budgeted for this case study, although this would have provided more depth to the case study analysis. Alongside the academic texts (in English) that we utilised, we also reviewed policy and practice reports, which included national and local energy planning documents, and newspaper articles (of which the majority were in Danish).

While doing the document review for describing governance practices over time, and for investigating the three different repowering case studies, we frequently made use of online translation services in order to access the policy and planning texts and public information originally written in Danish, thereby somewhat overcoming the language barrier limiting our investigation. This practice was highly beneficial to our work: we managed to greatly expand the information we could utilise and analyse for the purposes of our investigation. As described in our methodology section, we sampled these documents through inputting various Danish and English keywords into search engines and databases (including specific websites of important actors in the MidtVest region, and Denmark in general), and cross-referenced translations from the different translation services (primarily DeepL and Google Translate) and online bilingual dictionaries.

In terms of our **sampling** process, since we did not have pre-existing connections to any Danish actors or institutions, we utilised publicly available information in our investigation. The keywords and themes we used to identify policy and planning, as well as academic documents for literature review, were based on the main concepts addressed by the JustWind4All project and structured around the research questions we had defined in advance. We defined/delineated a focus on “repowering” for the report based on insights from the member of our research team based in Denmark, given his experience with

researching the Danish energy sector; and based on the fact that JW4A focuses on understanding governance issues around repowering as one of the yet untapped resources for accelerating wind energy development. The predefined focus also impacted our sampling process and how we searched for literature/documents to include in our analysis.

We **triangulated** the information we gained from conducting the literature review of our academic literature with the review of policy and planning documents/news articles, and with the data we gathered from the in-depth interviews. By combining these research methods, we expanded our investigation, the insights available to us, and the sources that our data derived from. To triangulate our methods and sources effectively, we integrated information from the literature review and the interviews according to the research focus and central concepts we had originally defined (of which “procedural justice” and “distributive justice” are the most significant). Subsequently, we were able to cross-reference the data we had gathered from each research method to confirm the correctness of our information and insights.

4 WIND REPOWERING AND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN MIDTVEST

4.1 REPOWERING DURING THE PRE-PERIOD 2000-2010

As mentioned above, Denmark has a rich history in wind energy. Which in turn means that repowering has been part of wind energy development for some time. In 1999, as part of energy reforms, grants were given to replace smaller wind turbines (<100 kW) (Agnolucci, 2007). As part of this reform, the developer got a fixed feed-in tariff rate as well as the right to buy shares in jointly owned wind parks (Agnolucci, 2007). This first repowering scheme was implemented from 1999 to 2003 (Gorroño-Albizu, 2018) with the goal to increase the capacity and efficiency of wind turbines (Munksgaard & Morthorst, 2008). This policy has proven to be successful as 1208 fewer turbines were needed to increase the overall wind energy capacity to 202 MW (Sperling et al., 2009). The second was implemented from 2004 until the end of 2010, and was aimed at turbines with a capacity of <450 kW. In the earlier scheme, depending on the distance to already installed wind turbines, the owner got 2 to 3 times the price supplemented relating to the decommissioned capacity. With the second scheme this was twice the amount (Gorroño-Albizu, 2018).

The beginning of the second repowering scheme was not as successful, due to the investment and related lack of profits of changing the turbines to more efficient ones as well as difficult site location (Munksgaard & Morthorst, 2008). The difficulty lies that in Denmark, renewed placement of wind turbines requires the re-approval by the relevant government agency, municipalities for onshore projects as well as potential reallocation of the newer turbines to more suitable sites. However, after slow initial uptake, the amount of turbines that either wholly or partially fell under the repowering scheme at the end was 348 MW compared to the initial goal of 175 MW (Sperling et al., 2009).

While it is unclear if there is an exact correlation between repowering and a decrease in community ownership during this period (1999-2010). What can be seen is that during the first repowering scheme, the installed capacity of citizen-owned wind turbine installations was higher compared to the second repowering scheme (Gorroño-Albizu et al., 2019). Interestingly, only during the end of the second repowering scheme (2009-2010) higher rates of turbines were installed compared to the earlier programme, indicating that the initial bottlenecks were overcome. From 2010 until 2016 the per year installed capacity of wind turbine parks owned by citizens dropped as large investor ownership increased. While not reflected in the cumulative installed capacity, it could indicate a shift in trend. In the case of Denmark citizen ownership also entails that a large chunk of especially early wind turbine owners were single citizens and not communities (Gorroño-Albizu et al., 2019).

To curb the total domination of wind turbine ownership by large investors, in 2009, as part of the Renewable Energy Act, the Danish government stipulated that developers should offer at least 20% of the ownership to local citizens (van Est, 2022). Due to the average lifespan of wind turbines in DK which is 18 years (Turbines, 2022) it is currently unclear to what extent community ownership has been impacted by these measures.

4.2 CURRENT REPOWERING

4.2.1 CURRENT GOVERNANCE PRACTICES WITH REPOWERING 2010-2023 (NOW)

For repowering and onshore wind turbine development in general, there are various schemes in place aimed at distributing some of the gains from wind energy. These schemes are enacted nationally and applied to the local context by the appropriate agencies, which may be national but are more often regional, like the municipalities who administer the “green pool”. Four main policies were originally outlined in the **Promotion of Renewable Energy Act**, which was first introduced in 2008, which aim to encourage local acceptance of wind turbine projects. These are the following: 1) a compensation scheme for local residents (the Loss of Value Scheme for Neighbours) related to loss of property value; 2) a co-ownership scheme (the Buyer’s Rights Scheme), through which 20% of turbine ownership shares must be offered for sale to local inhabitants; 3) a community benefit scheme, also known as the first Green Fund, and 4) a Guarantee Fund for local ownership initiatives (Johansen, 2021).

The **Guarantee Fund** is intended for local groups initiating wind farm projects, and applies for onshore and offshore wind projects. The loan guarantee is a maximum of DKK 500,000 [approx. EUR 67,060] per wind project, which is provided by Energinet (Denmark’s transmission system operator) as long as the turbines are not installed for the personal use of the owner (International Energy Agency, 2021). There are certain conditions: amongst other technical and financial considerations, the group initiating the wind project has to consist of at least 10 members, of which the majority had to either have permanent residency within 4.5 km of the project site, or live within the municipality of the planned project (Johansen, 2021). Another policy called the **Bonus Scheme**, which is also administered by the Danish Energy Agency, grants residents living closest to renewable energy plants the right to an “annual bonus”, paid to them by the plant owner and based on the plant’s production (Danish Energy Agency, n.d.). A **scrapping scheme** is also described in the Renewable Energy Act, as a certificate that is earned by replacing old and inefficient wind turbines with new ones (like repowering); which subsequently allows an installer to receive a price supplement (International Energy Agency, 2021).

All of these schemes and funds are used to improve the distributive aspect of wind energy development in Denmark. The paragraphs below describe how these schemes are enforcing distributive justice and how they operate.

4.2.1.1 The Loss of Value Scheme for Neighbours

Following Sections (§) 6-12 of the Act on the Promotion of Renewable Energy (VE Act), in Executive Order No. 122 of 6 February 2015/Executive Order No. 1288 of 27 October 2016, residents are allowed to seek compensation for property value loss resulting from nearby wind turbines. The **Loss of Value Scheme for Neighbours** (*Værditabsordning for Naboer*) was originally established around 2009 through the Renewable Energy Act (mentioned in the

introduction). This loss-of-value scheme is managed and administered by the Danish Energy Agency (DEA) through the Danish Wind Turbine Valuation Authority (*Taksationsmyndigheden*), an independent public authority established by the Ministry of Energy, Supply and Climate; and with ties to the DEA. The DEA acts as the secretariat for the Valuation/Assessment Authority, and the Valuation Authority evaluates and determines the compensation.

According to § 7 of the Act, the Valuation Authority makes a decision as to whether, pursuant to § 6 of the Act, the installer must pay for loss of value to the owner, on the basis of an individual assessment. The Valuation Authority must make an individual assessment based on the specific local conditions; thereby taking into account the character of the area and property prices in the area, whether wind turbines have already been erected in the area, whether there are other technical facilities in the area, as well as the distance of the wind turbines from the buildings, the height of the wind turbines and expected adverse effects from the turbines. Residents are able to claim compensation if the estimated loss in value due to the wind turbine projects exceeds 1% of the residential property's value: see the Act's Executive Order No. 1288, Section (§) 6, subsection 4.

Related to this scheme, maximum noise limits for wind turbines are defined. These are defined through Order No. 1736 of 21 December 2015. This states that the noise from wind turbines in the open country must not exceed 42 dB(A) at a wind speed of 6 m/s and 44 dB(A) at a wind speed of 8 m/s. However, there are no limits set for noise at other wind speeds. The executive order's maximum total limit for low frequency wind turbine noise is 20 dB. There are also conditions regarding the visual impact and shadow casting of the wind turbines.

4.2.1.2 Buyer's Rights Scheme

The right-to-buy or **buyer's rights scheme**, which also follows the stipulations of the Renewable Energy Act No. 1288 of 27 October 2016, means that a wind turbine developer/installer is obliged to offer 20% of the total project value to local citizens for purchasing, and to inform the community of this possibility. An exception is granted for projects involving "test" turbines or turbines erected for one's own use/consumption; here, offering a percentage of the shares is not obligatory (International Energy Agency, 2021). Citizens who live closest to the wind turbines, with a residence registered at a distance of up to 4.5 km from the installation site, and who are 18 years or older at the time of the tender, are entitled to buy shares largely at cost price. This procedure involves local residents submitting bids within an 8-week period from the date the tender is announced.

4.2.1.3 Green Pool

The **green pool** (*Grøn Pulje*) is an adjacent initiative intended to replace the original Green Fund. It was initiated on a national level by the Danish Energy Agency in 2019, but is administered locally by the municipality where a wind project is based (Energistyrelsen Center for Vedvarende Energi, 2019). The green pool is a lump sum which is allocated/paid to municipalities by the project developer when a renewable energy project is implemented; there are certain regulations about how to use these funds (Berggreen, 2023). Generally, its purpose is to promote municipal incentives for increased renewable energy development. This one-off payment is calculated per MW that is newly connected to the electricity grid.

The municipality administers the funds, which constitute a “green pool” and calls for applications from citizens for green community projects (Danish Energy Agency, 2019). Under this system, residents can apply for funding of up to DKK 200,000 [approx. EUR 26,823] per project, and create applications for several projects: the projects must be linked to one or more of the action areas in the Green Strategy: waste, water and energy, electricity, construction and renovation, indoor climate and chemistry, green areas and biodiversity, and it must be beneficial for all of the residents in the area in some way (fsb, n.d.).

4.2.1.4 Original Green Fund

The first green fund/support scheme was a community benefit scheme, which was introduced as the third policy measure related to wind energy development in the original Renewable Energy Act of 2008. The fund acted as a subsidy for projects or initiatives created for the benefit of local citizens: this meant projects promoting and enhancing renewable energy resources on a municipal level (Johansen, 2021). Individual municipalities were responsible for requesting financial support from the Green Fund, which generated DKK 88,000 [approx. EUR 11,802] per MW of wind power installed. While it was active, the Fund was relatively effective in accelerating wind energy investment. However, the Fund expired on 20 February 2018, after which the Danish government switched to a tendering process.

Section 18 of the Renewable Energy Act states that the payment of subsidies was conditional on the wind turbine in question having been connected to the electricity grid (Retsinformation, 2008). However, this condition did not require wind turbines to be fully operational to receive the subsidy: they simply had to have produced and delivered kilowatts before the expiry date (Jensen, 2018). This aspect is relevant for the case of the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines, where the project was fast tracked into approval and construction in winter 2017, so as to still receive the subsidy before it ended in February 2018. This was done despite there being no transformer station in place with enough capacity to process the increased energy produced by the new turbines (Jensen, 2018).

4.2.1.5 New Green Fund

One of the most recent initiatives to accelerate green energy and “phase out” the use of fossil fuels in Denmark is the new **green fund**, established on a national level in June 2022 (International Energy Agency, 2023). This is an investment of EUR 7.2 billion over the period of 2024 to 2040, which is directed towards funding projects and investments in green energy and the climate. Based on this, it was decided that Denmark will add 4 GW of offshore wind power by 2030, quintupling the current capacity, and will quadruple solar and onshore wind energy production as well. Regarding the CO₂ tax reform, it was decided for the country to take major steps towards achieving its 70% emissions reduction by 2030, cutting 4.3 million tons of CO₂, ensuring stability, and providing support for heavily impacted companies to prevent job and emissions relocation (Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities, 2022).

4.2.1.6 Procedural Justice and involved actors concerning repowering

As mentioned in the current developments, in terms of the Danish and EU definition, repowering is referred to using the exact same location but changing part or the whole wind turbine and putting a new one in place (Energistyrelsen, n.d.). If a project conforms to this definition, it allows for a fast track in permit approval. If however, the more broad term of repowering is applied, like the one being used in this report, a longer deadline of 2 years is applied. Reducing the permitting time has advantages, as new turbines, in theory, can be installed more quickly, this results in more positive impact in terms of emission reduction. However, reducing the time could affect how thorough the procedure is. Both human and non-human actors are included differently in the process while realising repowering wind farms: the following section describes the actors in more detail, as well as the relationships they have with other actors.

1. Human Actors

Local municipalities have many responsibilities in the permit procedure of a wind/repowering project. There are **designated areas** for wind turbine projects set out by each municipality, delineated by a Municipal Plan that is set for a certain timeframe: however, in some cases where a wind turbine project goes beyond these boundaries, an addendum to the municipal plan is created to accommodate its development. One other major task that municipalities are required to undertake is the creation of a **Local Plan** for any large construction project like a wind project. This begins with a “debate phase” that invites ideas and proposals for the planning process. Then, the municipality creates a proposal for the local plan, which is subsequently published for a period of 8 weeks; a second “hearing” or “public period” during which local residents are able to make comments. After this, the city council discusses to what extent they can incorporate comments and make amendments. This local feedback is then used to prepare a final version of the Local Plan, which is published and made publicly available. There are also two information sessions for residents, in the very beginning of a project (which is facilitated by the wind turbine developer), and during the planning process. Having two public hearings/meetings with local residents is required by national law for every onshore wind project in development (Interview 3, 2023).

However, even with this procedure in place, involving significant consultation and planning, a published local plan does not guarantee the **realisation** of a wind project that has been approved by the municipality. Instead, it is the responsibility of the energy company in the given area to ensure that there is sufficient capacity/facilities in place to receive the energy created by the new wind project (Planklagenævnet, 2020). This procedural condition can create delays and inconvenience human actors: as in the case of the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines, the lack of a transformer station with enough capacity to process the energy created by the repowering project meant that the turbines were unusable and inoperable for a period of time following construction (Jensen, 2017b). As a result, local residents in the surrounding area could not experience any benefits of increased energy production, or any returns from the shares they had invested in (if any).

2. Non-Human Actors and the Environment

In terms of non-human actors, like animal and plant species, as well as the environment in a broader sense, there is an extensive environmental assessment procedure associated with onshore wind projects. This process is required for repowering projects as well as greenfield wind turbine installations; even though repowering projects involve the installation of wind turbines in the same (or similar) location where turbines already exist, a new environmental

assessment is still required. In this way, the procedure for repowering projects is basically identical to that of greenfield developments. The municipality has the responsibility to publish an **environmental impact assessment (EIA)**, abbreviated to VVM in Danish) prior to installing the wind turbines, and must always be done when wind turbines are over 80 metres in total height. The municipalities were assigned the authority for the environmental assessment procedure (replacing the Danish Environmental Protection Agency) for wind turbines over 150 metres following amendments to the Environmental Assessment Act (*Miljøvurderingsloven*), which entered into effect on 22 February 2021 (Miljøstyrelsen, 2021).

The municipalities in MidtVest typically consult with many different authorities to complete this assessment. In the case of the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines, for example, these actors included the Roads Directorate (*Vejdirektoratet*, responsible for the Danish national road network), Energinet (Denmark's electricity grid operator), Museum Midtjylland (who provided feedback related to archeological factors), and Denmark's Nature Conservation Association (*Danmarks Naturfredningsforening*). Monuments and ancient settlements are protected under the "Museums Act" (*Museumsloven*): this states that an archeological assessment/investigation must take place before any developments or construction work begins, and that construction must be halted or relocated if any archeological artefacts or sites are discovered (Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune, 2021). Actors frequently involved in repowering procedures include the Danish Transport Agency (*Trafikstyrelsen*), the Danish Business Authority (*Erhvervsstyrelsen*), the Danish Environmental Protection Agency (*Miljøstyrelsen*), and various regional actors like neighbouring municipalities. The feedback from these various actors is utilised by municipalities to develop the EIA, a local plan, and any potential municipal supplement required for a wind repowering project.

The non-human actors considered in the EIA also include birds, bats, salamanders and deer, through assessing the project's potential impact on biodiversity. In terms of the environment and other non-human species, certain guidelines in accordance with the **Environmental Assessment Act (*Miljøvurderingsloven*)** and under the **Nature Protection Act (*Naturbeskyttelsesloven*)** stipulate that any wind turbine construction within 300 metres of the edge of a forest is prohibited (through the "forest construction line" or *skovbyggelinje*), as is construction within 150 metres of a body of water (labelled "lake/sea protection line" or *skyttelseslinje*). There are also laws concerning the **peace forest (*fredskov*)**; these are areas of forest placed under protection and designated as a "peace forest" under the **Forest Act (*Skovloven*)**, where § 11, subsection 1, prevents any buildings or facilities being constructed in these areas (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017). However, cases like the Midtjyske Motorvej turbines demonstrate that sometimes, projects are granted exemptions from these guidelines (see Section 4.3.3).

4.2.2 IMPLICATIONS OF REPOWERING ON THE WIND ENERGY SECTOR IN DENMARK AND TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENTS

As mentioned in the introduction, repowering is not as straightforward, even if currently a large chunk of the installed capacity is completed by repowering (Kitzing et al., 2020). Kitizing et al. (2020) describe that in the period of 2012-2019, repowering decreased the net number of turbines by 1, while increasing the capacity substantially. Interviews held with Siemens Gamesa and another Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) revealed that in some cases,

old projects can last for a decade more than initially expected, which postpones repowering plans to the future. In practice, even decommissioning is postponed and occurs, according to another OEM, only when the expenses associated with operation and maintenance surpass the benefits gained from electricity production. The costs of decommissioning is also stated as another reason for not taking down the turbine (Interview 2, 2023) and potentially repowering. This limits the amount of renewable energy that can be generated because it is often the case that repowering leads to fewer wind turbines but higher installed capacity and power production. Therefore, delays in repowering mean that energy that could have been produced is not.

From the material perspective, if decommissioning is chosen as the option, it means that wind turbines do not undergo a second life but some of its components are. Within the turbines itself, there are various metallic components, which can be recycled. The revenue generated from selling these metals to local scrap dealers plays a pivotal role in supporting local metal recycling initiatives. Nevertheless, a critical aspect of decommissioning pertains to non-metallic components, which currently lack established recycling techniques (Interview 1 & 2, 2023). Moreover, while the industry has the capability to recycle blades easier, ultimately the customer decides if these options are used (Interview 2, 2023). Often they do not end up going for this option as it is more expensive. Policy could therefore help in imposing targets in order to reduce the environmental impact of currently installed wind turbines.

While some metallic materials can be recycled, substantial Rare Earth Elements (REE) elements are needed to develop wind turbines. A unified and European strategy in securing REE is recommended to secure future development of wind energy (Interview 1 & 2, 2023). According to the interviewees, it is important to develop a rigid supply chain based on environmental, social, and governance (ESG).

Beyond that, there are efforts at an EU level via thorough investigation, scaling-up, and validation- of a number of novel technologies, tools, and operational approaches to assist wind farm owners, operators, and investors in making well-informed decisions to maximise the economic performance of their assets. This is done by weighing lifetime extension, effective decommissioning, and full or partial repowering in order to take advantage of the increased circularity of wind energy systems. There are two options: complete repowering, which is a more involved process that entails the decommissioning of the original and the installation of new turbines and foundations, and partial repowering, which replaces individual components.

However, the lack of experience with systematic, industrialised decommissioning practices should be pointed out. By highlighting the significance of governance in setting recycling standards, the sector is now working to develop recycling procedures and resolve such problems. It seems reasonable that larger clients may proactively adopt best practices without necessarily governmental mandates due to their significant investments. But for other practices this demands a framework in place as soon as possible.

Last, despite being significant providers, the OEMs have little direct power over many regulatory issues towards a more efficient governance in the sector. But it is crucial to participate actively in industry networks and talks regarding the difficulties in acquiring permits. These permit-related issues can increase project risks and financial worries,

affecting both ongoing projects and future prospective investments. The growing use of renewable energy necessitates a reevaluation of energy strategies in addition to regulatory considerations. The industry is aware of the need for greater regional and circular practices that make use of locally produced renewable energy. It is important to keep in mind that there is frequently more energy produced than needed due to the expansion of renewable energy sources. This excess begs the concerns of how to change energy consumption patterns and increase energy efficiency as well as storage, especially with offshore wind generation. Onshore repowering could have a role in this as well, if done effectively and perhaps coupled well with demand or storage/hydrogen, could help accelerate the Danish energy transition further. That said, the impact of these changes will affect both human and non-human actors in various ways. It is therefore recommended that considerations are made when repowering turbines as well as their impact on the surroundings.

4.3 COMPARISON OF REPOWERING PROJECTS IN MIDTVEST

In order to get a better understanding of how repowering affects various actors and how current legislation and governance is enacted, three repowering case studies are outlined below from a distributive and procedural perspective. These are the Krejbjerg repowering project in Skive Municipality, the Sdr. Bork Vindpark in Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, and the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines in Ikast-Brande Municipality.

4.3.1 *Krejbjerg*

The Krejbjerg repowering project consists of 6 wind turbines that are replaced by 3 new ones (Redaktionen/MBBP, 2016). The new turbines will triple the installed capacity of the old turbines. Following the passed 20% community ownership regulation, the residents have been offered shares of the project. The project also received subsidies from the original Green Fund scheme, which amounted to over DKK 800,000 [approx. EUR 107,295] in this case (Redaktionen/MBBP, 2016).

The Krejbjerg project was owned by Krejbjerg Vindkraft K/S, a limited partnership established in 2014 by 6 local landowners (Welander, 2017a; OWRN, 2023). However, the project was met with significant public opposition, due to residents fearing health-related consequences as a result of low-frequency noise generated by the turbines. The project was also delayed while it was investigated whether the turbines would disturb a protected species of bat in the area. Because the project “dragged on” while electricity prices fell, the local landowners behind Krejbjerg Vindkraft sold the project to HOFOR, the largest utility company in Denmark (Welander, 2017a). HOFOR is largely owned by the city of Copenhagen and 8 other municipalities close to the capital, and undertakes various services related to water and energy management; including heating, gas, and wind turbine installation

(HOFOR, n.d.; HOFOR, 2018). HOFOR overtook the management of the Krejbjerg project through its subsidiary company, HOFOR Vind A/S.

3. Distributive justice

In Krejbjerg, following the regulations in place at the time of repowering (2017), affected neighbours were compensated following the “loss of value scheme” (Krejbjerg Vindmøllelaug I/S, 2017). For the Krejbjerg project this means that the affected neighbours got compensation before the new wind turbines were constructed. Determining the amount of compensation is done by the Taxation/Valuation Authority, following the procedure outlined above.

Following the buyer’s rights scheme, citizens are entitled to become shareholders of the project. In the case of Krejbjerg it means that citizens can become owners before the project is up and running and are expected to share in the made costs of the project (just like a normal developer would) (Krejbjerg Vindmøllelaug I/S, 2017). Only a given set of shares can be bought in the wind park. Priority is given to inhabitants that live less than 4.5 km away from the closest turbine. Furthermore, shares are first divided so that everyone can obtain at least one, after which citizens are able to obtain multiple ones. In total there were 6673 shares available for the citizens to procure at DKK 3200 per share [approx. EUR 420]. The shares were fully subscribed to, meaning all 6673 shares were purchased (Energistyrelsen, 2017).

4. Procedural justice

In 2009, the Danish Ministry of the Environment and Energy enacted circular no. 9295 which holds municipalities accountable for exploiting the wind resources but also takes into account neighbouring residences, nature, landscape, cultural, historical and architectural interests. Following this circular, municipalities have to find designated areas where wind turbines can be developed. In the Skive Kommune plan, distance restrictions to nearby houses are set in place as well as blade size to hub height. Also noise restrictions are put in place that fall in the bracket of normal background noise. Starting in 2011, low-frequency noise limits were also put in place. It is also possible that noise measurements are taken after the project.

As part of the repowering procedure, Skive, the municipality where Krejbjerg is located, prepared an environmental impact assessment (EIA) following Danish national legislation (Skive Kommune, 2014). Next to this, Skive has decided to couple the EIA report with an environmental assessment. This report contains the environmental impact as well as human health and how these factors can be monitored. The plan that was submitted to the municipality was in the same area the municipality had allocated space for the development of the turbines. The location of the new turbines did not overlap with the to-be-replaced turbines. While the location of the turbines was chosen as much as possible to be away from the residents, further distances were not possible due to the search area defined by the municipality. This search area was defined in the Skive Municipal Plan 2013-2025.

The Skive Municipal plan takes several factors into consideration in deciding a relevant development location. For example, coastal zones are not primarily possible mainly due to tourism and recreation activities. Close to the site, Skive has defined some of the surrounding areas as “areas of special landscape value” (based on natural, cultural-historical, geological or landscape value). In addition to the municipal plan, Skive also

enforces extra regulations mainly pertaining to the visual ease of the wind turbines. For example, residents cannot be affected more than 10 hours per year from shadows. In the case of Krejbjerg the wind turbines are regulated as such so that they do not violate these requirements.

Non-human actors are taken into consideration when planning in the Krejbjerg case, but only up to a degree. Loss of habitat is assessed following the impedance of wind turbines on nature reserves. Low mortality rates amongst animals, e.g. birds, are also deemed acceptable by the municipality. Following an investigation, the protected bat species that caused concern and delayed the project was deemed to not be negatively affected by the wind turbines, and the project was cleared for construction (Welander, 2017b).

Next to the possible harmful effects of the wind turbine on both human and non-human actors, the positive impacts associated with wind turbines are also taken into consideration, such as a reduction in both CO₂, SO₂ and NO_x emissions by using wind turbines to create renewable energy.

Judging purely from the environmental assessment, the considerations of both human and non human actors are taken into account. However, it is unclear whether the concerns of the human actors impacted the process or whether the results of the assessment were able to fully address the concerns of the inhabitants or affected communities (which appeared mostly related to low-frequency noise). Opinion pieces submitted in 2014 by residents of Skive Municipality to one of the local newspapers, Skive Folkeblad, complain about the plans to install “giant wind turbines” and label them an “assault on nature”, due to their large size and proximity to nearby residences (Vestergaard, 2014). They also reference concerns expressed by future neighbours of the project, who question whether they will become “humans as laboratory animals” (Rechnagel, 2014), a comment which perhaps references the feared health risks associated with low frequency noise. An article written about a woman moving to Skive to experience nature and the rural idyll of Jutland describes her peaceful lifestyle being disrupted when “Copenhageners came and set up 140 metre high wind turbines in her backyard”, referring to the Krejbjerg project as well (Vibjerg, 2021). It is unclear whether these points of contention were addressed in any public meetings with citizens or press releases from the wind turbine installer, and there is no record addressing any official complaints made about the project.

What is taken into account is the comparison between the new and old wind turbines mostly in terms of visual impact on the surrounding environment. This is a stark difference between repowering and green field developments, as in the base scenario there are of course no wind turbines. It seems that repowering projects therefore have extra leverage when compared to greenfield projects. This extra leverage can also be seen in the fact that most of the wind turbines that have recently been installed in Denmark fall under repowering.

4.3.2 Sdr. Bork Vindpark

Sdr. Bork Vindpark is located in the municipality of Ringkøbing-Skjern, near the border of the municipality of Varde. The Sdr. Bork Wind Park repowering project consisted of 5 new Vestas wind turbines replacing 19 old ones and was completed in early 2022, thereby “upgrading” the 25-year-old wind park. Representatives of Sdr. Bork Vind K/S stated that the 5 new turbines would deliver more than four times as much energy, delivering approximately

120 million kWh per year at 31 MW of installed power: by comparison, the now-decommissioned turbines, which were erected in 1997-1998, delivered approx. 23 million kWh per year at 11.4 MW installed power (Momentum Energy Group, 2023). Citizens living in close proximity to the wind park had the option to purchase shares equivalent to 10% of the project (Torp, 2023a).

The newly commissioned turbines are classified as “test” turbines, given that this type, the Vestas V162-6.2 MW land-based turbine, is still rare and being implemented for the first time using Vestas’s latest technology. The Danish Energy Agency (DEA) approved the “test status” of the turbines. This also means that Vestas will monitor the data related to the turbines’ performance, as will the board of Sdr. Bork Vind K/S (Tornbjerg, 2022). According Section 13 of the Act on the Promotion of Renewable Energy, the designation of the turbines as “test” turbines means that the law to offer at least 20% of the turbines ownership shares for sale to citizens does not apply in this case.

The actors involved included the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, Vestas, Energrid, Momentum Energy as the project manager, the local community, local landowners and owners of the old wind turbines. The company behind the current repowering project, Sdr. Bork Vind K/S (where “K/S” signifies a limited partnership business), is made up of local landowners and the 21 owners of the original wind turbines, and was founded in December 2013 (Tornbjerg, 2022). Environmental impact assessments were completed and planning permission was granted on 14 March 2021, then the Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune granted its final municipal approval at the end of summer 2021 (Torp, 2023a). The turbines were connected to the grid on 22 December 2022, and officially inaugurated to a crowd of local community members on 13 January 2023 (Torp, 2023a; Momentum Energy Group, 2023). The entire process from executing the project to commissioning the new turbines took less than 16 months (Torp, 2023a), which is relatively fast for a wind project of this scale.

5. Distributive justice

As mentioned previously, citizens or “neighbours” of the wind project were given the option to buy shares of up to 10% of the total value of the project. According to news articles, the local community surrounding the wind turbines is supported with a fixed annual amount, and those citizens who live closest to the turbines are able to buy shares “largely at cost price” (Tornbjerg, 2022). Residents were informed about the investment scheme on 29 June 2022 during a meeting at the Assembly Hall in Sdr. Bork (Sdr. Bork Vind Nabo I/S, 2022). Under the **green fund scheme**, some local shareholders partially report high levels of satisfaction with the outcomes, describing a stronger “sense of belonging/connection” once they can also economically benefit from the turbines’ installation (Tornbjerg, 2022; Skaanning, 2022; Torp, 2023b).

To enable investment in the 5 new wind turbines, the company Sdr. Bork Vind Nabo I/S was set up: this company then became the largest shareholder in Sdr. Bork Vind K/S, holding 11,616 K/S shares out of a total of 116,908 K/S shares (equivalent to 9.94% of the company) (Ny Vindpark Sdr. Bork, 2022). Residents of legal age, who had reached the age of 18 before 14 March 2022 and were living within 2.25 km of the nearest wind turbine of the Sdr. Bork Wind Park, had the opportunity to buy **shares** first. In this first drawing round, residents purchased 8,006 interest shares. Following this, there were 3,580 I/S shares left on offer in the second drawing round, for residents living within 4.5 km of the nearest wind turbine. The price per I/S share was DKK 3,550 [approx. EUR 475]. All persons were able to buy up to

50 shares, if they had not previously subscribed for shares in the first subscription round (Sdr. Bork Vind Nabo I/S, 2022).

The shares were fully subscribed to (Ringkøbing Landbobank, 2023). This implies that many local residents were able to take advantage of becoming financially involved in the wind project; or at least, that there was significant interest from residents in the immediate area. However, it might be the case that some residents purchased far more shares than others, thereby making the distribution less even. There is also little information on how much of a return residents have received on their investment since the repowering project was completed: as a result, the outcomes regarding distributive justice for local community members are not clear cut.

As part of the **Renewable Energy Act** of 2020, the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality receives a one-off payment of DKK 125,000 [approx. EUR 16,746] from the wind turbine installer per MW connected to the grid (Sdr. Bork Vind Nabo I/S, 2022). The municipality has full control over the administration of these funds, which constitute a so-called “green pool” (*Grøn Pulje*) that is primarily intended for green initiatives and projects which nearby residents apply for (Ny Vindpark Sdr. Bork, 2022). Given that the wind park will deliver energy at 31 MW of installed power, this means that the one-off payment amounts to almost DKK 4 million.

However, given that this project specifically is quite close to the border of Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, to the point where some of the impact is already perceived in the neighbouring Varde Municipality, this has meant that up to 56.8% of the almost DKK 4 million in “green money” generated by the wind park will be sent to Varde municipality instead, thereby flowing out of the “local community” as one news article puts it (Skaanning, 2022). The chairman of the technical and environmental committee calculated the division of the funds this way, given that both Varde and Ringkøbing-Skjern municipalities are within a radius of 4.5 kilometres from the turbines (Skaanning, 2022). Hans Østergaard, the mayor of Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, made a statement about sharing the funds equally to benefit citizens in the immediate area (regardless of which municipality they live in), a few months after some complaints from Varde Municipality residents who felt inadequately compensated (Reintoft & Breum, 2021). These residents perceived themselves as not receiving as much money from the “green pool” as they deserved, considering the context of how expensive the project is/how much money is available (Reintoft & Breum, 2021). However, an agreement was reached which determined that projects from Varde Municipality would also be able to obtain support (Ny Vindpark Sdr. Bork, 2022). The DKK 3,750,000 [approx. EUR 502,518] from the “green pool” will be released to municipality residents according to the aforementioned percentages.

Generally speaking, residents of an area neighbouring a wind project are also compensated for the potential decrease in their property’s value through the **Loss of Value Scheme**. However, there are no verdicts for the Sdr. Bork Wind Park registered on the Valuation Authority database. The implications of this are unclear: it could be that because the project is relatively new, verdicts for resident compensation have not yet been reached, or that no compensation claims have been registered with the Authority yet. And in terms of environmental effects on non-human actors, the **environmental report** (*Miljørapport*) indicates that the Sdr. Bork project complies with all nationally determined limits for noise, visual impact, and shadow casting; and that it will not have any significant impact on the

cultural and natural landscapes in the area, or on biodiversity (Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune, n.d.).

Significant construction had to take place to realise the Sdr. Bork Wind Park repowering project. In **material** terms, this involved having to break up the 4 metre deep concrete foundations of the old wind turbines and prepare new ones, which each consist of “90 tons of steel and 900 cubic metres of concrete” (Tornbjerg, 2022). Of this old material, the decommissioned turbines themselves, the iron and the concrete of the foundations were recycled, with the latter being used for road material: however, Tornbjerg (2022) mentions that moving the concrete is perhaps not the most “climate-friendly” solution. The material for the new foundations, including the pipes and cables required for each turbine, was delivered by up to four trucks at a time, from early morning to late afternoon. Because of the large rotor diameter of the turbines, the blades cover an area of 20,612 square metres (Tornbjerg, 2022).

Based on this information, it appears that the surrounding community living within a few kilometres of the site was the area burdened with consistent construction work, which was frequent; and given how much material wind turbine construction requires, also seemed to be a large undertaking. In terms of **distributive justice**, the residents living close by experience a disproportionate “burden” of the project’s negative externalities (mainly construction noise and traffic) in comparison to the rest of the municipality. Therefore, it seems that the system of procuring shares in the project attempts to make up for this uneven distribution of consequences and differing impact on residents’ everyday lives, by granting those living closest to the wind park **priority access to shares**. Furthermore, these funds for the municipality are also intended to support green initiatives or projects for the renewable energy plant that close neighbours apply for (Ny Vindpark Sdr. Bork, 2022).

6. Procedural justice

The Sdr. Bork wind project was also unanimously approved, with 29 out of 29 votes in favour in the city council (Torp, 2023a). The Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality had the responsibility of granting building permission, which they did between spring and summer of 2021. A “dialogue meeting” also took place, which residents of the community were invited to attend, and where they were informed about the possibility of buying shares (Torp, 2023b). The project was decided on *without* input from the whole local community (it was approved solely by municipality), but the option for local residents to purchase shares did affect the level of local support: two local residents of the village of Sdr. Bork described feeling a “stronger sense of belonging” upon being able to profit monetarily from the project (Torp, 2023b).

Another aspect relating to procedural justice is that the repowering project is rooted in, and was initiated by, a **locally**-based group (in the form of Sdr. Bork Vind K/S). Even though the company’s members were not representative of the entire community, nor democratically elected/voted on, the simple fact that members of the community participated in the process of setting up the repowering project seems to have had a significant impact on the public perception of the wind farm (Tornbjerg, 2022; Torp, 2023a; Torp, 2023b; State of Green, 2023). Articles written about the project discuss how it is “powered by locals”, mention the strong collaboration between different wind actors and local landowners, as well as the project’s unanimous approval in the vote by the city council (State of Green, 2023). They emphasise the “local forces” behind Sdr. Bork Vind K/S by discussing how the

partnership was established in a local inn, and discuss the financial benefits for the citizens of the area in detail (Tornbjerg, 2022). The fact that project shares available to the public were fully subscribed to, and that most public statements given by citizens are wholly positive and also emphasise the benefits of local ownership, seems to support this idea.

One important factor to consider is that the local members of Sdr. Bork Vind K/S had to invest into the wind park repowering project: this involved capital of approx. DKK 5 million [approx. EUR 670,170], and this money that could have potentially been lost in the case that Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality had not granted building permission. This demonstrates that there is a **high economic standard** for involvement in wind energy projects like this: investors must be in an economically advantageous position in order to participate, given that the deposit was set at DKK 100,000 per person [approx. EUR 13,400] (Tornbjerg, 2022). So in some ways, investment and/or significant involvement in a wind energy project is only possible after a certain economic entry point, which may have the effect of/contribute to socioeconomic stratification/inequity.

There is an extensive permit procedure associated with a wind project of this nature: the Sdr. Bork repowering initiative had to pass an EIA/VVM environmental assessment, meet the requirements of the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, and handle “public consultation responses” (Momentum Energy Group, 2023). Given that the new turbines are over 150 metres high, the municipality had to develop and publish an EIA statement. Sdr. Bork Vindkraft K/S had originally requested that the Danish Environmental Protection Agency assess the project in accordance with section 18(2) of the **Environmental Assessment Act** (*Miljøvurderingsloven*). However, amendments to the Environmental Assessment Act (mentioned previously), transferred the authority for the environmental assessment of wind turbines over 150 metres to the local municipality in which turbines are installed, in February 2021. As a result, the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality became the environmental assessment authority in connection with the environmental assessment of the test turbines at Sønder Bork (Miljøstyrelsen, 2021).

The new turbines had to fall within a designated wind turbine area, as described in the municipal plan. **Local Plan No. 444**, published on 9 August 2021 by the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, is a detailed description of the different factors involved in the planning process for wind energy: it maps out the environmental conditions in the surrounding area, existing regulations and planning requirements, and lays down provisions for how the new construction will be placed and designed in the given area. The municipality is required to create a local plan for any large construction project of this nature. The Sdr. Bork repowering project is not in accordance with the existing municipal planning framework, meaning that an **addendum** had to be created as a supplement to the local plan: this is Addendum/Supplement No. 15 to Municipal Plan 2021-2033. Both the local plan and the Supplement No. 15 were adopted on 8 February 2022 (Sdr. Bork Vind Nabo I/S, 2022).

Various actors and various considerations were involved in planning the setup of the repowering project. For example, in terms of safety regarding air traffic, the turbines were required to have light markings on the nacelle: a flashing white light during the daytime and a low intensity red light throughout. The final decision regarding light marking had to be made by the Danish Transport Agency (Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune, 2021). The planning also involved intensive assessment of environmental, geological, and even archaeological

factors; and evaluating how groundwater, the features of the landscape, neighbouring buildings, and nature-related legislation would impact the project.

After the city council has fulfilled their responsibility of drawing up a proposal for the local plan, the plan is published for 8 weeks: in this time, citizens and local residents can make comments and propose changes. The hearing period for this project took place over the course of 5 weeks, from Monday 26 November to Monday 31 December 2018: according to the municipality, the comments received were included in the preparation of the local plan (Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune, 2021). Following this “public period” the city council discusses to what extent they can incorporate the suggestions and make amendments. Clearly, there is an opportunity for the local residents to be involved in the process, but the final decision still lies in the hands of the municipality. In this case, **PlanEnergi**, a Danish company that provides consultation, planning, and mapping/organisational services specifically for renewable energy projects, prepared Local Plan No. 444 in collaboration with **Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality’s** planning department. The plan includes an analysis of the area, background information on the project, an assessment of the environmental conditions and how the project aligns with EU nature protection laws, noise calculations, and stipulates other requirements for the setup of the turbines. The local plan explicitly designates approx. 900 metres of **new service roads** to be built within in relation to the wind turbine project; as well as the widening and/or strengthening of existing field roads; and states that they must be built along “existing elements” in the area such as field dividers and hedges. The plan also defines specific access points to the site of the wind project (Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune, 2021).

Michael Shalmi, a representative for the Momentum Energy Group (which was in charge of the project management for Sdr. Bork) describes that significant care was taken to minimise possible road obstructions, and to ensure that construction would have a minimal impact on the surrounding community. Residents of the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality mention that the area became significantly “busy” during construction (Torp, 2023b). Given the process described in the local plan, it seems that residents did have some say in the project and voicing any concerns with noise or the construction process in the public forum stage in 2021: however, they did not have a final say in the decision making, so there was no guarantee that their complaints would lead to any alterations. The Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality was in charge of originally proposing the locations and conditions for the project.

The project was significantly delayed from the time of the first application in 2012/2013, due to national interest in the Sdr. Bork area as a possible site to place larger “test” wind turbines, given its good distance from neighbours. Therefore, the interest of national authorities delayed the project until an arrangement could be established, and the “test” turbines were the ones installed in the end in 2022 (Interview 3, 2023).

Referring back to the **Addendum/Supplement No. 15** to the municipal plan - the wind turbines do not fall within the designated zone, so Addendum No. 15 has extended the boundary of the area for wind turbine installation. Additionally, the 5 wind turbines have a total height of 180 metres, which goes beyond the maximum of 149.9 metres set in the framework regulations of the municipal plan. This addendum ensures that Local Plan No. 444 (related to Sdr. Bork wind farm) is in accordance with the Municipal Plan for Ringkøbing-Skjern. This seems to have been done (or at least proposed) without consulting local

residents of the area; presumably, they had the chance to object or suggest improvements during the “public period”, given that the supplement was published openly at the same time as the local plan (Ringkøbing-Skjern Kommune, 2021).

4.3.3 Vindmøller ved Midtjyske Motorvej

The repowering project alongside the Midtjyske Motorway in Ikast-Brande Municipality involved the replacement of 4 old wind turbines with 10 new ones. The project was finally approved by the Ikast-Brande Municipality in 2017 and completed in early 2018: it was a cross-municipal project in collaboration with the neighbouring Vejle Municipality, where 4 of the 10 new turbines were erected. In order to realise the project, 10 homes within the project area were demolished. The developer acquired the homes through voluntary acquisitions, but it was not completely clear how many homes would be demolished and which would be utilised for other purposes (Taksationsmyndigheden, 2018).

The municipalities originally received the application for the project in 2015. In the initial stages of the planning process for the wind project, the municipalities held a public consultation from 23 September 2015 to 21 October 2015 (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017). In May 2016, the Ikast-Brande Municipality put the planning of all wind turbine projects on hold until latest 1 February 2017. However, by 4 January 2017, the Vejle and Ikast-Brande Municipality administrations were meeting with the wind project’s manager and representatives from Siemens Gamesa. Following this, a first proposal for a local plan was submitted for consultation on 21 February 2017 in Ikast-Brande Municipality. This began an 8-week consultation/public period, where residents could submit comments and responses, and a citizen’s meeting/information session also took place during this time, on 23 March 2017 (Jensen, 2017b).

The Ikast-Brande Municipality approved the repowering project through Local Plan No. 331 and Municipal Plan Supplement No. 44 (complete with an EIA statement) on 26 June 2017. Subsequently, the Vejle Municipality approved the project via Local Plan No. 1223 and Municipal Plan Supplement No. 36 (with their own EIA report as well) on 29 June 2017. A change was reported to both the Ikast-Brande and Vejle municipalities on 27 September 2017, stating that the wind turbine type used in the project would change from a Siemens SWT-2.3-101 model to a Siemens SWT-3.2-101 model: as a result, the wind turbines would have a capacity of 3.2 MW each, instead of 2.3 MW as originally planned (Bjerre, 2017). The total maximum height of the new turbines was 130 metres (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017). Both municipalities issued the building permit for the wind turbines on 9 October 2017 (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017).

The annual production of the 10 new wind turbines was estimated at approximately 60,000 MWh at their total of 32 MW of installed power, which corresponded to the annual electricity consumption for appliances and lighting in approximately 17,600 households in 2014. In connection with the installation of the 10 new wind turbines, four existing wind turbines were taken down: three 1.3 MW wind turbines at Svindbæk and one wind turbine on the company Welcon’s area of 600 kW (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017). This indicates that the repowering project led to a significant increase in energy production capacity; also due to the fact that the general number of wind turbines increased as well.

The new turbines were erected at the beginning of 2018, at which there was no capacity to utilise the power they produced. This only changed on 1 May 2018, when Ikast-Brande Municipality's engineering and environmental committee approved an application to build a transformer station at Brandevej 55 (Lund, 2018).

During the project, there was massive neighbourhood opposition to the project and the erection of the new turbines was widely contested by residents of the area who live near the highway in question (Lund & Jensen, 2017b). The reasons for this widespread disapproval will be discussed further in the section on procedural justice.

K/S Svindbæk Vindkraft was the limited partnership responsible for the construction of the 10 wind turbines along the highway, which they did alongside the company Ecopartner. The partnership was originally founded in Aarhus by Allan Dahl Larsen (project manager and partner in the company Ecopartner) and Ole Buch Skadhauge (project manager and co-owner of K/S Svindbæk Vindkraft) on 8 July 2015. Both Larsen and Skadhauge have been, and are still today involved in numerous renewable energy projects throughout Denmark, specifically focusing on wind energy. It is unclear what their motivations were in initiating the project and how much they invested in it: Skadhauge lives in the area where the wind turbines were erected, but it is unclear what Larsen's connection is (Lund & Jensen, 2017a). However, according to the Danish Business Authority, the two officially resigned as managers of K/S Svindbæk Vindkraft on 3 October 2017 (Erhvervsstyrelsen, 2023), a few days after the project was granted final approval, but before the wind turbines could be built.

Ownership of the project transferred fully to a Danish developer based in Søborg, European Energy A/S, under its chief executive Knud Erik Andersen, on 30 September 2017. There was uncertainty as to why this sale happened: Lund and Jensen (2017a) comment that it does not appear to be for financial reasons. The original founders did not make any public statements about the matter, and there is limited information about the sale of the partnership. Then in December 2019, European Energy sold 7 of the 10 wind turbines to an unnamed German investment management company (based in Hamburg), while retaining ownership of the remaining three (reNEWS, 2019).

7. Distributive justice

In the first public information session held on 23 March 2017, wind turbine installer **K/S Svindbæk Vindkraft** informed citizens about the new wind project and the possibility of receiving compensation for potential loss of value of their property (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017). Residents in the area surrounding the wind turbine project (specifically, within 6x the total height of the turbines) were eligible for compensation under the **loss of value scheme** (in accordance with provisions of the Renewable Energy Act). Local residents of the area submitted a total of 20 compensation claims to the Danish Wind Turbine Valuation Authority in relation to the project, and the authority conducted their inspection and investigated the cases throughout November 2017. Following this, the Valuation Authority reached verdicts on 10 August 2018, more than 8 months after the claims were submitted, that the wind turbine installer should pay a total of DKK 1,495,000 [approx. EUR 200,309] to compensate residents for the loss in value of their property as a result of the new wind turbines (Taksationsmyndigheden, 2018).

In another information meeting on 7 December 2017, the wind turbine installer K/S Svindbæk Vindkraft officially informed residents about their right (if they were 18 years or

older at the time of the tender, and their residence was registered at a distance of up to 4.5 km from the installation site in Ikast-Brande or Vejle municipality) to acquire shares in the wind turbine project. This follows the stipulations of the **Renewable Energy Act, Act No. 1288** of 27 October 2016 (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017). This “right-to-buy” scheme meant that K/S Svindbæk Vindkraft was obliged to offer 20% of the total project to local citizens for purchasing: this procedure involved local residents submitting bids within an 8-week period from the date the tender was announced on 22 November 2017.

Given that the total expected production of the project was 68,307,000 kWh, this corresponded to 68,307 shares of 1,000 kWh in total. Therefore, under the **buyer’s rights scheme**, 13,661 shares of 1,000 kWh (20% of the total project) were offered for citizens to purchase. The cost price per share was DKK 3,800 [approx. EUR 509] (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017). The act of buying shares meant becoming a co-owner of Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, the limited partnership established for the project and operating wind turbines 3 and 5: it also meant becoming liable as stakeholders in the partnership (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017). However, of the 13,661 shares offered to residents of the area, only 52 had been sold by the end of the 8-week tender period (which took place from Wednesday 22 November 2017 to and including Wednesday 17 January 2018) (Energistyrelsen, 2018). It is unclear why this is the case, but a potential explanation for this is that residents were aware that there was no transformer/substation with enough installed capacity to receive the energy produced by the new turbines, meaning that the turbines would likely not be in operation for a few years to come (Jensen, 2018). As a result, the citizens would likely have to wait a while to see any returns from their investment into the project. This factor could have contributed to the lack of local investment into shares.

Despite the procedure for compensation and purchasing shares appearing almost identical to any other wind project, public opinion of the repowering at the Midtjyske Motorvej appears to be quite negative. This is evident from a public opinion forum and news site, Brande Bladet, for residents of the former Brande municipality (before it became Ikast-Brande). There are many articles published about the project: some discuss how opponents of the wind turbine projects are “fighting on”, debate whether the turbines have been “illegally erected”, and express frustration that the municipality is not taking the complaints of neighbours seriously. The dissatisfaction of community members is also reflected in a document published by the “Planning Appeals Board” (in Danish: Planklagenævnet), which extensively addresses various complaints made by citizens in 2017 which attempted to appeal the approval of the project. There are three main complainants mentioned in the report, of which Complainant 2 is a single resident, and Complainants 1 and 3 are actually a group of local residents. After evaluating the various factors at play, especially regarding the environmental report, the Planning Appeals Board concluded that the complaints were not valid and dismissed the case: this also meant that the fee citizens had to pay to submit an appeal were not refunded. This decision was also made after a significant processing time, given that it was only published on 14 December 2020.

8. Procedural justice

Similarly to the aforementioned projects, the planning for the wind turbines next to the Midtjyske Motorvej involved an environmental impact assessment (EIA) statement and an environmental report, featuring extensive technical analysis of various factors. Special emphasis was placed on assessing the turbines’ visual impact on the landscape, noise and shadows cast on neighbouring homes, and nature in general (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune,

2017). The Ikast-Brande and Vejle municipalities both collaborated on this report, given that the 10 wind turbines are located in **both municipalities**, and it was first published in January 2017. This adds another dimension to the planning procedure, given that both municipalities received the project application, collaborated on the environmental report, each created their own separate local plans for the project, and each proposed a supplement to their respective municipal plans in relation to the project.

The Ikast-Brande and Vejle municipalities first organised a **public consultation period** related to the project from 23 September 2015 to 21 October 2015. This “debate phase” invited ideas and proposals for the planning process (Planklagenævnet, 2020). Appendix 5, Section 1.3 of the final local plan describes comments the municipalities received during this period (this non-technical summary is also featured in the EIA report). In general, residents were concerned about possible alternative locations for the project, the impact of new turbines on wildlife like bats and birds, the potential health risks of increased noise, falling property values and the depopulation of rural areas; and expressed a desire to see visualisations of the proposed turbines, as well as for green scheme funds to be used locally (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017).

Parallel to this, the municipalities consulted with different authorities to determine the content of the EIA statement. These actors included the Roads Directorate (who requested a visualisation of the turbines from the perspective of the motorway), Energinet (who warned that the turbines would have to comply with distance regulations), Museum Midtjylland (who recommended a test excavation to ensure the safety of possible archaeological finds in the area), and Denmark’s Nature Conservation Association (who recommended an investigation of the project’s impact on bird and bat wellbeing). The municipalities utilised this feedback to develop the first proposals for their respective local plans and municipal supplements pertaining to the wind turbines on the Midtjyske Motorvej. Vejle Municipality adopted its final municipal plan **Supplement No. 36** regarding the wind turbines, as well as a proposal for a related Local Plan No. 1223, on 25 January 2017.

Subsequent public meetings further informed residents in the surrounding area about the wind turbine project: for example, the aforementioned public information meeting on 23 March 2017 informed residents about the possibility of receiving compensation for any loss of value of real estate, and also presented the planning proposals for the project (Svindbæk Køberetsselskab I/S, 2017). There was a second 8-week **public consultation** period between 22 February and 21 April 2017, during which consultation responses were received related to the municipal proposals and associated environmental reports. After considering these responses, the two municipalities published the final version of their respective plans. Ikast-Brande Municipality adopted final municipal plan **Supplement No. 44** and **Local Plan No. 331**, complete with the associated EIA report, on 26 June 2017. Vejle Municipality adopted final **Local Plan No. 1223** and its associated EIA report on 29 June 2017 (Planklagenævnet, 2020).

It appears that all of the concerns mentioned by residents and organisations above are extensively addressed and investigated throughout different chapters in the final local plan (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017). The final versions of the local plan and the municipal supplements for Ikast-Brande and Vejle municipality discuss various considerations. They state that **construction work** is expected to take up to 25 weeks, given that this involves the existing wind turbines in Vejle municipality being taken down, as well as the erection of the

new turbines and connecting them to the electricity grid. The plan also suggests reducing the construction time by working outside of normal working hours. The plan goes on to describe the predominantly agricultural landscape and vegetation of the area, and states that approximately 1,900 metres of field road will be strengthened, and approximately 1,700 metres of new **access roads** will be built to support the construction of the wind turbines (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017). In terms of environmental considerations, the municipalities make the assessment that there are no protected animal species in the wind turbine area, and that it is not a significant area for bat or bird activity.

However, the local plan also states that the project has been granted an **exemption from certain environmental guidelines**, namely the “forest construction line” (which prevents any construction with 300 metres of the edge of a forest) and the “lake/sea protection line” (which prevents any construction within 150 metres of a body of water), and also requires the clearing of a small area of a “peace forest” for installation of two of the wind turbines - to replace the area that will be cleared, the Danish Nature Agency requires the planting of an area of forest twice the size (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017). Given that the Midtjyske Motorvej project was granted these exemptions in the first place, as illustrated in the figure below, it is worth questioning how effective these environmental regulations are in protecting non-human actors.

Figure 4: Forest construction line, lake protection line, peace forest around Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbine row (Ikast-Brande & Vejle Kommune, 2017)

Figure 7. Forest construction line, lake protection line, peace forest and §3 nature around the wind turbine row 1:25,000

Signature:

- Local plan boundary
- New wind turbine with blade projection
- Access road/service road
- Forest construction line
- Sea protection line
- Peace forest
- § 3 nature

The project also necessitated the creation of a municipal addendum/supplement that expands the area available for siting of the new wind turbines, because the planned location of the Midtjyske Motorvej turbines was not within a framework area for wind turbine siting in the original municipal plan. The two figures below illustrate, firstly, the seven new wind

turbine areas added to the municipal plan alongside the maintained wind turbine areas, and secondly, the ten wind turbine areas that must be removed from the municipal plan so that there is space to install the new ones. These changes made by the Ikast-Brande Municipality show how the siting of the Midtjyske Motorvej turbines was made possible.

Figure 5: The map shows the seven wind turbine areas that the City Council lays out in the municipal plan with Supplement/Addendum No. 24 (Ikast-Brande Kommune, 2013)

Figure 6: The map shows the 10 wind turbine areas that must be removed from the Municipal Plan, in order for new turbines to be erected (Ikast-Brande Kommune, 2013)

Even though the procedure of establishing this repowering project appears similar to the Krejbjerg and Sdr. Bork projects, and despite significant consultation with residents of the area, the public perception of the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines appears to be **largely negative**. The public forum and news site Brande Bladet, as well as the newspapers Vejle Amts Folkeblad and Horsens Folkeblad, describe significant neighbourhood opposition and various political procedures carried out against the project. This disapproval of the project is related to various factors, which are also mentioned in the complaints analysed by the **Planning Appeals Board** in their report from 14 December 2020 (mentioned above). The first of these complaints was submitted by a group of citizens on 2 August 2017, around a month after the two municipalities finalised their planning for the wind project.

As mentioned above, the Planning Appeals Board report describes three different complainants (where Complainant 2 is a single resident, and Complainants 1 and 3 are a group of local residents), with complaints primarily concerning the environmental and noise assessments, insufficient visualisations of the project, an alleged lack of neutrality of the council, the involvement of the public, and the alleged abuse of power of the municipalities. Ikast-Brande and Vejle municipalities respectively responded to the complaints on an individual basis shortly after they were submitted, and then more extensively in this document. The first complaint relates to the alleged lack of neutrality of a council member involved with approving the project, due to his profession as a real estate agent supposedly showing homes to the residents displaced/bought out by the wind project: the municipality disputed this claim, stating that council member was not involved with showing the home to the resident in question. The environmental assessment was deemed as not thorough enough; with complainants citing worries about the habitats of species like bats, newts, and birds, as well as the potential impact of “stray currents” on farm animals. In response, the

municipality argued that these species were in fact mentioned and their wellbeing sufficiently addressed in the environmental report (Planklagenævnet, 2020).

The complainants also alleged that the potential noise levels were insufficiently assessed; specifically that despite complying with set limits for noise, there is no calculation of the impact that this noise would have on the surrounding environment, and no assessment of the cumulative noise produced by all new turbines (Planklagenævnet, 2020). In response to this, the municipalities stated that they had completed the assessment in line with the nationally determined regulations for noise (Planklagenævnet, 2020). Another significant point of contention was a complaint regarding lack of involvement of the public and a perceived “abuse of power” by the municipalities for pushing the project. Complainants stated that information sessions took place during public holidays, and that **they lacked information** about the project, since they experienced delayed or insufficient access to key documents related to the case, and that this had prevented them from engaging with the case to the extent that they wanted to. In response to this claim, the municipalities stated that they had endeavoured to respond to all requests for document access “within the rules” (Planklagenævnet, 2020). Furthermore, all three complainants agreed that the municipality had deliberately “rushed” the planning process for the benefit of the developer, so that the project could be completed before the **end of the green fund/support scheme** in February 2018. The complainants argued that “disproportionate consideration” had been shown towards the financial benefit of the developer, to the detriment of the local residents of the area: they reinforced this conclusion with the fact that the wind turbines would demonstrably only be put into operation (and connected to the electricity grid) up to a year after construction, making the irrationality of pushing the project forward clear. In response to this, the municipalities simply stated that they had complied with the requirements of the Planning Act regarding the involvement of the public in the planning process (Planklagenævnet, 2020).

Later complaints are related to a last-minute change in wind turbine capacity and other circumstances surrounding the Midtjyske Motorvej wind project, and are featured in various newspaper articles. These include the fact that people were still living in the 10 houses purchased for demolition by the wind turbine installer when the construction of the wind turbines began, and the fact that the municipalities approved the change in turbine capacity without conducting a new environmental assessment. Residents argued that people still living in the **acquired houses** during wind turbine construction was illegal; but according to other involved actors, legislation states that houses must only be vacated once the wind turbines are connected to the grid/start spinning, and claim that the residents misunderstood the policy in place (Jensen, 2017a).

The other significant issue that there was no **transformer station** with enough capacity to process the energy produced by all 10 new turbines is discussed numerous times in different news articles, and was also mentioned in the Planning Appeals Board report. The existing 150/60 kilovolt (kV) transformer station in Thyregod has an available capacity of 4 MW; not nearly enough to accommodate the 32 MW capacity of the new turbines. To receive a subsidy from the renewable energy scheme, the turbines had to be in operation by 20 February 2018: to fulfil this requirement, the turbines had to spin a single time before the date (Jensen, 2018). The Planning Appeals Board/municipality responded to complaints about this issue by stating that a local plan does not guarantee the *realisation* of a wind project: rather, it is up to the energy company responsible for the area (in this case,

RAH/MES, the result of two energy network companies merging) to ensure that sufficient energy capacity is present and apply for the necessary permits to build a new transformer station (Planklagenævnet, 2020). Building a new 60/10 kV substation and cable connection is a slow process, and the municipalities only approved the building of a new station in May 2018 - about four months after the turbines had already been erected. Furthermore, a new transformer station of this size was not mentioned in the local plan that formed the basis of the project, even though local authorities were aware of the situation (Lund, 2018). Newspaper articles state that as a result, the wind turbines will not be useful for a few years at least (Jensen, 2018). It is unclear whether this size transformer station was built in the end: the annual report for 2022 released by the energy company RAH NET A/S describes the building of two new 150/60 kV transformer stations at Thyregod in the summer of 2022, almost four years later, but does not mention whether this project was related to the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines/whether this was the approved station in question.

A report titled “Decision on Non-EIA Obligation - Project Change in Wind Turbines at Midtjyske Motorvej” describes the project change from a Siemens SWT-2.3-101 wind turbine to a Siemens SWT-3.2-101 model. It was possible for residents to submit complaints based on the municipality’s decision not to create a supplementary EIA statement for this **change in turbine capacity**, and in general, via an online complaints portal. However, there was a fee of DKK 900 [approx. EUR 120] for private individuals and DKK 1,800 [approx. EUR 241] for companies and organisations to make a complaint: in certain cases, exemptions from this fee were possible (Bjerre, 2017). It appears that many residents were unhappy with the change in the type of wind turbine used in the project, and **felt that the environmental assessment of the repowering project was no longer valid** after this change, given that it had been conducted based on a smaller capacity model. Meanwhile, the Planning Appeals Board and municipalities estimated that the difference in noise would not be significant enough to warrant a new environmental assessment (Planklagenævnet, 2020). Throughout the local plan and the public planning process (information released to citizens), it is only ever mentioned that the wind turbines will have a capacity of 2.0-2.5 MW each - so the change to a larger capacity turbine model and the almost immediate approval of this project change by the municipalities (without conducting a new EIA) appears to have surprised residents, who did not feel adequately informed or consulted about this change. Essentially, the repowering project that was approved for construction in the end was different to what they had anticipated.

In the Planning Appeals Board report, the municipalities alleged that the type of wind turbine that was included in the environmental report had been withdrawn from the market, meaning that the larger capacity turbines were a necessary change. However, a newspaper article disputes this claim: according to Siemens Gamesa, the manufacturer involved in the Midtjyske Motorvej project, the 2.3MW turbines are still produced if ordered. Furthermore, the article provides evidence that EcoPartner, the company collaborating on the project, received a letter from Siemens Gamesa containing an overview for the order of 10 wind turbines each with a capacity of 3.2 MW on 30 January 2017 - more than six months before the company applied for an official project change through the municipalities. Evidence from internal emails between EcoPartner and Siemens also confirms that this larger model has been part of the planning process since at least December 2016 (Jensen, 2017b). This indicates that the project managers had already decided to use a larger turbine model far earlier in the process, but only reported the change later on - meaning that all of the municipal planning documents and assessments were based on a smaller capacity wind

turbine model. According to the administration, with the **larger capacity model**, the low frequency noise produced doubles (Larsen, 2017). The Planning Department of Vejle Municipality stated that at a wind speed of 8 m/s, the **low frequency noise** would increase by up to 4.3 dB(A) in comparison to the 2.3 MW model, which is an audible change. However, they also calculated that at 6 m/s, the low frequency noise would be reduced by up to 1.7 dB(A) in comparison to the lower capacity model (Bjerre, 2017). Despite the assessment carried out by the municipality, which justified not creating a new EIA assessment, citizens believed that this change in the turbine capacity made the previous EIA invalid, and felt blindsided given that the project managers did not inform the public about the change until very late in the planning process.

The project has also led to some **political disputes**. The political parties Dansk Folkeparti, Konservative, Ismail Yalcin (now called Den Social-Liberale Liste) and Fælleslisten had all voted against the wind project back in June 2017, while the parties Socialdemokratiet and Venstre (who constituted a majority) voted in favour of it. Then in November 2017, Ismail Yalcin of the Social-Liberale Liste party requested a renewed political examination of the Midtjyske Motorvej project by the city council: this led the mayor of Ikast-Brande Municipality at the time, Carsten Kissmeyer, to state that he had never experienced an occurrence like this before in his political career (Jensen & Lund, 2017b). Some political figures like Simon Vanggaard of the Danish People's Party (*Dansk Folkeparti*), who voted against the wind turbine project, expressed frustration with the system, stating that “the model we have now does not seem to work. We end up running over citizens in the local area completely”. Vanggaard also expressed frustration that the project change to the wind turbine capacity had been approved on the basis that the 2.3 MW model had been discontinued, when this was apparently untrue, citing a need for accurate information, especially for a situation like this “where there are many emotions” involved, especially those of homeowners in the area (Jensen, 2017c).

The biggest issue in this case, which sets it apart from others, therefore seems to be the **lack of citizen involvement** in the project (Jensen, 2017c). Despite this repeated public and political opposition to the wind project, it remained approved by the municipality. Residents of the area like the complainants, and people mentioned in newspaper articles describe a feeling of frustration that their voices are, in a sense, going unheard, and that municipalities have “ignored” the protests of neighbours (see titles of said newspaper articles).

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Generally speaking, wind repowering holds an important role for onshore wind projects in the MidtVest region. The following section describes the distributive and procedural justice aspects of repowering projects in this region, where our analysis investigates how these different aspects are taken into account in different ways when developing repowering projects. We explored this on the basis of the following questions:

1. What role does distributive and procedural justice play in repowering in the MidVest region of Denmark?
2. To what extent does repowering in MidtVest enact distributive and/or procedural justice?
3. How has repowering affected the justice of wind energy development in the MidtVest region of Denmark?

4. What are the implications of (not) repowering on wind energy development in MidtVest?

In short, the repowering process in MidtVest (and Denmark as a whole) seems to enact a relatively good level of **distributive justice**: there are numerous policies in place focused on financial compensation for neighbouring communities of wind projects, and efforts are made to ensure that those living closest to the projects are prioritised. Furthermore, there is the possibility of citizens becoming shareholders in the project. However, improvements can be made, see recommendations.

In terms of **procedural justice for non-human actors**, the process also seems relatively thorough; there is extensive consideration of different environmental factors, especially biodiversity and animal species, which is carried out by various experts throughout the environmental assessment process. However, many repowering projects fall short when it comes to **procedural justice for human actors**: only two information meetings with the public are required, developers are not legally obligated to facilitate a dialogue with the local community, and there is a lot of local debate, opposition when it comes to further developing onshore wind and a lack of transparency. These factors are discussed in more detail in the following paragraphs.

Considering the last research question, repowering in our definition does not affect the wind energy development process nor the distributive or procedural part. That said, when streamlining governance with regard to repowering, care should be taken to not impact these negatively. Yet there is a chance to do this in a way such that wind power projects remain community owned and are able to be more quickly repowered.

5.1 *Distributive Justice*

Financially speaking, citizens are encouraged to participate and feel a sense of local ownership in repowering projects like these through purchasing shares in the project under the **buyer's rights scheme**, a co-ownership scheme originally inspired by Denmark's history of local wind cooperatives. However, there are also barriers to participation: given that shares can be relatively expensive (ranging from EUR 420 to EUR 509 in the cases above) and that investing depends on residents' socioeconomic situations, this does not guarantee that all members of the surrounding community will be able to financially benefit from wind repowering projects. Additionally, this scheme has been criticised: some consider the 20% offered to be too little, in that it does not ensure community participation or "ownership" until far later in the process; that the money shares generate does not adequately compensate for "perceived local losses" (Gorroño-Albizu, et al., 2019, p.6); and that people who are opposed to the project do not purchase shares in the first place - as was the case with the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines. Johansen (2021, p.10) describes how despite aiming towards distributive justice, this scheme paradoxically tries to provide a top-down monetary solution to the impacted residents, when the actual goal is community involvement from the bottom-up.

Furthermore, the initial investment that most repowering projects require is beyond a typical household budget, and even the budget of a wind cooperative (Johansen, 2021, p.6). This means that investment is risky, and there is a high financial threshold to becoming involved: this is a sentiment residents surrounding the Sdr. Bork Vindpark shared, with some expressing a wish for a lower financial threshold for local investment/ownership in wind and

repowering projects.

Another matter of public interest is the money from the “green pool” and how it is used to benefit which groups of people. In the case of the Sdr. Bork Vindpark, there was some debate about where this money should go, given that many residents of the neighbouring Varde Municipality also live close to the new wind turbines. After some complaints from Varde residents (who largely made up the group opposing the repowering project) about feeling excluded from the project’s financial benefits, despite having to deal with the shortcomings of living close to large wind turbines (see Reintoft & Breum, 2021), Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality agreed to share the money. In the end, ca. 60% of the green pool funds went to Varde Municipality, thereby evenly distributing the nationally-determined financial compensation in a more “fair” way, to those actually affected by the project. As Skaanning (2022) puts it, almost DKK 4 million in “green money” flowed out of the “local community” with this ruling. This begs the question of what is fair in the situation: the wind project is located completely within the Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, and therefore only this municipality has the decision making power regarding the project. However, the presence of the newer, bigger turbines also affects the residents in nearby Varde; yet, their municipality is not involved in any part of the planning process. Our third interviewee stated that this redistribution of the green pool across a municipal border was actually not legal at the time (the municipalities discovered this afterwards), but the national law was subsequently changed to allow the practice (Interview 3, 2023). This suggests that local actions focused on enhancing distributive justice in repowering can feed into larger, national policy changes, perhaps making them more equitable.

The DEA’s Centre for Renewable Energy reports that the green pool initiative was created in response to criticisms of the previous green scheme (which applied to the Krejbjerg and Midtjyske Motorvej projects); residents had complained that municipalities often did not use the funds for projects benefiting the residents who were actually affected by wind turbines, but rather invested them elsewhere in the municipality (Energistyrelsen Center for Vedvarende Energi, 2019).

Given that the visual impact and noise generated by wind turbines are the biggest reasons for complaints by residents in the vicinity, most repowering projects promise to reduce this inconvenience, while also generating greater returns for the community by increasing energy efficiency and production. For example, the Sdr. Bork repowering project was incredibly positively received; given that 19 old turbines were replaced by only 5 new ones, this greatly reduced the visual impact the turbines had on the area. News reports about the wind project describe the area as becoming “calmer” with the decommissioning of the old turbines and their replacement with the newer, and fewer, turbines (Tornbjerg, 2022). Contrastingly, the Midtjyske Motorvej project led to an overall increase in the number of wind turbines, by replacing 4 old turbines with 10 new ones - this project proved highly unpopular amongst local residents, in part due to their fear of being negatively impacted by increased noise. It seems that repowering initiatives are mainly appreciated when they take up **less space in the landscape**: public opinion is often more positive when the projects free up the landscape and lead to a reduced visual impact on their surroundings. Interestingly however, the Krejbjerg repowering project does not clearly align with this point. The project still faced significant public opposition, even though it involved reducing the number of wind turbines in operation from 6 to 3. This is likely due to the fact that the new turbines were significantly taller and larger than the old ones, thereby having a comparable (or perhaps greater) visual

impact.

However, some factors related to justice can be improved upon. For example, regarding distributive justice, in the Krejbjerg project, funds were not made available for the citizens, with the exception of the direct payouts at the start of the project. Only, in terms of buying up shares, which did cost 420 euros each, was it possible to take part (in only a part) of the project. What would have been better in terms of distribution would be to allocate funds to the public or a public organisation that could utilise the money for the community, like the green pool, or to make the shares divisible into more affordable chunks. Some citizens have a similar opinion, expressing a desire for green energy to be “even more locally rooted” to the point where all citizens are able to benefit, and not just those with the money to invest in shares (Torp, 2023b).

Legislation in Denmark has determined maximum limits for noise created by wind turbines at different wind speeds, as well as for low-frequency noise, and visual impact (like height restrictions, but not for shadows cast). Approved projects have to comply with these regulations, and the three repowering projects in Skive, Ringkøbing-Skjern and Ikast-Brande respectively do so. Yet, given the fact that these projects have still received numerous applications from nearby residents for compensation under the Loss of Value Scheme (given that the presence of large wind turbines brought on by repowering) indicates that despite these regulations, citizens are still (to some extent) impacted by repowering projects - or they perceive themselves to be. Even though the number of wind turbines was reduced in the case of the Krejbjerg and Sdr. Bork repowering projects, residents mainly had an issue with the increased visual impact of the far larger, newer turbine models, when compared to the smaller and less visually impactful old turbines. Furthermore, in their compensation claims for the Krejbjerg and Midtjyske highway projects, many residents expressed concern that they would be negatively impacted by increased general noise levels as well as low frequency noise from the larger turbines. In the majority of these cases, the Danish Wind Turbine Valuation Authority conducted an investigation that resulted in residents being compensated between DKK 30,000 [approx. EUR 4,019] and DKK 250,000 [approx. EUR 33,498] each for their losses.

5.2 Procedural Justice

Between all three repowering cases, there are numerous common threads: given that they are all onshore wind projects, the **municipality** has a central role in the planning and approval process. Municipalities determine how much land is designated for wind turbine development, oversee consultation meetings with the public, and conduct various environmental and economic assessments are part of the planning process for a wind energy project. Various institutions and organisations (associated with fields like archeology, ecology, aviation) are involved in these assessments as well, each giving recommendations or advice related to their respective areas of expertise. This information goes into a Local Plan created for the project, which must align with the overall Municipal Plan: sometimes this is achieved through creating a supplement/addendum to the Municipal Plan, for cases where the planning area for the wind project does not align with the area designated for wind turbines (this was the case for all three repowering projects discussed above).

Residents do have some power in the procedure, since they are able to provide feedback on project proposals and submit official complaints. When it comes to official decision making

on whether a project should go forward, they are able to influence the outcome through their **elected representatives** in the city council (in Danish: *byrådet*), each of whom are members of different political parties. For the Sdr. Bork Vindpark, the city council voted unanimously in favour of the project, whereas for the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines, the political parties in the city council were significantly divided in their stance, despite the majority eventually voting in favour. From the cases above, it is evident that a variety of actors are involved in the repowering process; but that power is not necessarily distributed evenly between them. On the other hand, residents also have some direct power in that complaints they submit, especially regarding a possibly insufficient environmental assessment of the wind project, can significantly delay and in worst cases halt a project entirely (Interview 3, 2023).

In terms of procedural justice: The municipality determines which areas will become designated wind turbine zones, and decides when amendments will be made to the Municipal Plan (Interview 3, 2023). Local citizens are mostly only officially consulted in the two public meetings during the process of planning the wind project: aside from this, there can also be unofficial conversations with the project developer (if the developer chooses to enter into a dialogue with local residents), and residents can pay a fee to file an official complaint with the Planning Appeals Board.

In terms of procedural justice, Skive Municipality did take into account concerns of the inhabitants with regards to sound and visual pollution from the Krejbjerg project, and performed tests in the environmental report. However, it is unclear how big the role was of the citizens in deciding the particular area for the installation of wind turbines. Next to this non-human actors were taken into account, but certain impacts were either allowed or the operation of the particular wind turbine was adjusted.

Bureaucratic/extensive procedure: the advantages of this system, regarding procedural justice especially, are that it allows for a variety of considerations and it provides a lot of information - the downside is that extensive planning does not guarantee the **feasibility** or even the **usefulness** of a project. In the case of the Midtjyske Motorvej repowering project, the local plan was extensively planned out and highly descriptive, but there was no transformer station with enough capacity to utilise the energy the turbines produced: therefore, the end result was no increase in energy for at least another year or two post-installation (Planklagenævnet, 2020). Plus, even with an extensive consultation procedure which also invited complaints and feedback from citizens, and despite majority approval in the city council, the project was still viewed poorly by many residents, who felt as though their voices were going unheard/that their feedback was not actually implemented or taken seriously (Jensen, 2017c).

According to the urban planner from Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality, known as Interviewee 3, the wind turbine **developer** also holds a lot of power when it comes to the success of a project (Interview 3, 2023). This is because they have a significant role to play in facilitating dialogue with the local population and gathering their thoughts/opinions; Interviewee 3 argues that the developer engages with local citizens far more intensively and much more frequently than the municipality, who mainly carry out the planning process and the required assessments. This was the case for the Sdr. Bork repowering project, and arguably, the reason for its success and relative popularity with the local community. Partially because the developer was a local initiative made up of community members, there was frequent

engagement and awareness of the project. Interviewee 3 states that this would be the ideal situation for a wind project: i.e. having a developer who is highly involved, who values open dialogue, and who works with the community instead of making decisions that exclude them. This implies that there is an important role for the developer to fill when it comes to procedural justice in repowering. In terms of distributive justice, Interviewee 3 described the need for wind developers to create **local value** for citizens through the wind projects (Interview 3, 2023).

Local involvement is a factor that holds a lot of importance: especially in news articles discussing wind energy developments, locality (or lack thereof) is often emphasised as a central factor in project development (Skaanning, 2022; State of Green, 2023; Torp, 2023b). Discussions of “successful” projects often imply that local collaboration and approval signify a success. For wind projects that are not positively perceived by the local community and surrounding landowners - even if they are legally approved by the municipality - there is a lot of contention and significant delays in completing a project can occur, like in the Krejbjerg case. Repowering projects do seem more likely to generate local approval than regular wind projects, given that most of the time, repowering initiatives attempt to reduce the impact of wind turbines on the surrounding landscape, by replacing a greater number of small wind turbines with a fewer number of larger/more efficient ones.

The importance of community involvement could be related to the fact that Denmark’s long history of wind energy initiatives is related to local wind cooperatives, and there is resistance to newer projects that are more disconnected from the local residents, which are more associated with large wind corporations. It could also be that given Denmark’s extensive history with wind turbines and decades of wind energy development, citizens have grown tired of onshore projects, and may feel as though there is not enough “space” for a greater number of turbines on land - many residents express resistance to being inconvenienced by the construction, noise, and visual impact many wind projects bring. This is evident in the reports created by the Valuation Authority related to compensating residents for the loss of value they experience in their real estate. Complaints along these lines are present even in cases of repowering, regardless of possibly favourable outcomes in the long run (like economic benefits through shares and increased energy security). These widespread perceptions imply something about perceived procedural justice.

An increase in **marketization** in Denmark has disempowered the local cooperatives that originally spearheaded the wind energy sector, and as these procedural/legislative changes have been contested by citizens, there has been a shift in public opinion regarding onshore wind energy in the past decade (Kirkegaard et al., 2023, p. 657). Wind turbines have gone from enthusiastic popularity to a “sensitive issue”: in 2010, few municipalities felt “positive towards building new land-based turbines” (Möller, 2010, p. 234), and local opposition to onshore wind appears to be growing. Coupled with the fact that most wind turbines are repowering projects, it seems that repowering is a vital part of maintaining wind energy development in Denmark.

There is also an apparent conflict/point of tension between the **rural** and the **urban** (as well as between what is perceived as **local** and **non-local/foreign/global**) in repowering initiatives in MidtVest. The Krejbjerg case appears to exemplify this: once the project was sold to HOFOR before the turbines were installed, descriptions emerged of the project as an initiative that “Copenhagensers” were coming to Jutland to implement, thereby disrupting

and negatively impacting the “rural idyll” of municipalities like Skive (Vibjerg, 2021). The article by Vibjerg (2021) places significant emphasis on the narrative that the project is managed by outsiders rather than local people, and governed in a top-down manner by municipalities that do not have the best interests of local residents in mind. Relatedly, Gorroño-Albizu et al. (2019, p.7) argue that HOFOR’s strategy of investing in wind projects located outside of the Copenhagen Greater Area, for the purpose of meeting Copenhagen’s climate goals, is a system that seems to exclude the local communities where the turbines are installed from any significant form of ownership.

6 SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the analysis and discussion of this case study, it is clear that each specific repowering case reveals certain dilemmas and factors at play in the Danish wind energy sector. These involve factors concerning the involvement of local residents, the process of handling and accommodating an energy surplus (and other effects of repowering), and the role of transparency of different actors throughout the planning process. All of these points provide us with valuable information for formulating recommendations for just and effective wind energy governance.

In the Danish case especially, it becomes apparent that **repowering** is an effective way of increasing a country’s wind energy capacity. In densely occupied wind turbine regions, repowering can lead to increase in capacity as well as decrease in the overall number of turbines. Following our definition of repowering, it makes sense to regard new turbines as a new project, and not simply an upgrade to old ones. This is evident from the change of location and height, therefore affecting the environment and human actors differently.

6.1 *Distributive Justice*

Repowering projects can reduce the amount of **community ownership**: this is evident in cases like Krejbjerg, where the sheer size and scale of the project required investment from outside the local community. This is also a problem with other projects, as they can be difficult to manage and frequently require significant funding, meaning they are often sold to larger developers later on. The **green pool** or an adaptation of this could be used to fund locally based repowering projects, or to incentivize/subsidise local efforts to repower wind turbines nearby. Adapting or expanding this scheme/fund is recommended because its current form does not seem like it is enough to make onshore efforts like repowering seem more viable or worthwhile than offshore ones. This would also be an important strategy given that local resistance to wind projects often stems from a perceived lack of local involvement or agency; residents dislike feeling as though wind projects are imposed on them, and as though they have no say in deciding how wind turbines are implemented in their own neighbourhoods, so coupling it with procedural part of repowering is also essential. These recommendations for the green pool align with those made previously, by organisations like Green Power Denmark (see Berggreen, 2023).

6.1.1 *Concrete Recommendations to improve Distributive Justice*

- **Tailor the Green Pool** so that funds become available for locally owned repowering projects. More locally owned projects would positively impact inhabitants' opinions on wind energy.
- Give citizens a **bigger say** in how the money of the green pool is distributed/invested.
- Stimulate recyclability of wind turbines by ensuring that money from the green pool can be used to improve the recycling capabilities of repowered projects. This would also ensure compliance with circular design directives.
- Lower the cost of shares offered through the buyer's rights scheme to increase their accessibility to a greater number of residents.
- Maintain the "compensation claims" system of the Valuation Authority, as it seems to be an effective way to acknowledge and address citizens' concerns about their properties and neighbourhoods. Investigations are conducted in a thorough way, although not always very quickly (in the case of the Ikast-Brande repowering project, citizens waited more than nine months for a verdict/compensation regarding the loss of value to their real estate), so perhaps this process could be sped up.

6.2 Procedural Justice

One hurdle is that even though many repowering projects are theoretically the "same" project as before, just being upgraded, they still require new permits - a process which sometimes takes a considerable amount of time (Interview 1, 2023), meaning that investors often lose interest in this timeframe. Recent developments like the Marine Plan and the cancellation of the Open Door scheme have also obstructed the supply chain somewhat (as discussed in the interview with Siemens Gamesa). A strategy for truly accelerating onshore repowering projects could be significantly reducing the time a permit process takes to a maximum of a few months or weeks which the current EU Council Regulation from 2022 stipulates.

However, given that new wind turbines established during repowering projects in Denmark are often in locations that differ to the original/ageing turbines, and that they are significantly larger, it does seem justified that a new environmental assessment is necessary. Therefore, there is some risk associated with reducing the permit processing time, especially when it comes to public involvement/opposition. The tension here is that public consultation is often slow, complicated, and difficult for the developer to manage; on the other hand, **public opposition typically occurs** when wind/repowering projects are rushed or hastily implemented (might reduce the "justice" aspect of a wind initiative), and public disapproval significantly hinders the success of a project (as we can see in cases like Krejbjerg and the Midtjyske Motorvej wind turbines). Issues that might cause concern or annoyance for residents, like the shadow flicker effect, require certain impact assessments.

The Danish electricity grid is getting full and the interviews we conducted with the two OEMs have revealed that onshore wind and repowering initiatives are no longer worth it for manufacturers and investors, as it has become a priority for developers to go far offshore and place wind turbines there instead. Decommissioning is also a complicated process, so many owners choose to extend their wind turbine licence instead. Onshore repowering is important and should be pursued as a strategy to increase energy efficiency and capacity, but it needs to be promoted, so that actors in the Danish wind energy sector see it as a viable option for the future.

6.2.1 Concrete Recommendations to Improve Procedural Justice

There is an increase in capacity that results from repowering, which can lead to a **surplus of electricity**, but because there is already a lot of wind energy being produced, this surplus doesn't necessarily find its place in the grid. This is an issue that should not be overlooked. The Midtjyske Motorvej case indicates that more care should be taken to find alternative ways to store and use the energy *before* a project is completed, so it does not go to waste. For future repowering projects, it is important to find a solution to this surplus before the repowering occurs, and this aspect should factor into the planning process. In the Midtjyske Motorvej case, people were opposed partly because the installed capacity of the turbines ended up being greater than originally planned. This was also because there was no transformer station and/or grid connection to actually capture the energy produced by the turbines at first, so citizens felt as though the wind turbines were set up unnecessarily.

Transparency and awareness about changes is important every step of the way - people had to specifically request access to documents related to the projects, rather than the documents being available publicly on some kind of database (municipality had responded that they receive a lot of access requests which makes it difficult to respond/grant access in a timely manner), citizens complained that they could not be as involved in the case as they wanted to be, because they did not have full access to important information.

Dialogue sessions and exchanges are vital in the planning process: citizens often feel unfairly treated if procedures or proposals change last minute and they are not consulted/asked for their approval (like in the case of the Midtjyske Motorvej project), feel blindsided when policy decisions are made too "top-down" or seemingly to the disadvantage/against the desires of the majority of people - principle of democracy is perceived as key to the process. A good dialogue with the project owner is also key, according to Interviewee 3, and to the research project Wind2050, which investigated local acceptance of wind energy, and its related planning and policy measures in Denmark between 2014 and 2017 (CONCITO, 2011).

Denmark has an extensive analytical procedure and infrastructure for wind energy; a variety of actors are involved in planning and approving wind energy/repowering projects- this appears to be thorough and commendable - rules, regulations, and guidelines are publicly accessible, projects are presented publicly, citizens' opinions and recommendations are specifically requested when new projects are proposed/approved by the municipality, and information about the project planning is structured, extensive, and written in an accessible way. Yet, it also means that the system is quite bureaucratic, increasing complexity, wait time and even transparency. For example, the wind turbines along the Midtjyske Motorvej, where citizens only received a response/verdict related to their complaints three years later, when the turbines had already been approved and built).

6.2.1.1 Incentivising Repowering Projects

Another aspect of the issue is **financial**, given that the repowering process is typically costly and complicated: the current plan/framework does not benefit independent power producers (according to data from interviews). It is therefore more cost efficient for independent power producers to leave ageing turbines inefficient rather than repowering. The social impact of this is that old, ageing turbines occupy valuable (arguably limited) space that could be utilised for more efficient energy production. Owners even prefer to have wind parks switched off for long periods of time instead of servicing them/getting a service done (generally, they prefer to service the turbines on their own rather than contacting OEMs,

because the service is too expensive); in these cases, the loss of energy production does not negatively affect the owners, because they have generally already earned back their investment by this point. A way for the state to address this issue could be through **subsidising** this move to repowering/the continuation of the project. Another strategy to implement this could be extending the **licence** of a wind park for 2 years, on the condition that the earnings from power generated during this period goes to fund the repowering of the project.

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6.2.1.2 Reducing Permitting Times

Therefore, there is a need for nuance here that still takes procedural justice into consideration: perhaps, both reducing the permit processing time for a repowering project could be combined with a full commitment to transparency and consistently providing the public with access to all project-related documents and proceedings. With recommendations related to the municipalities, it is also important to consider how much power the municipalities have and the restrictions they have set on wind energy and how regionally-specific regulations and processes can be.

6.2.1.3 Supplying Materials for Repowering

It is essential for wind turbines to use REE. However, their supply is limited and/or restricted to various countries or locations making them rare. It is recommended that the EU creates a unified strategy that both ensures supply but also ESG compliance.

7 LIMITATIONS

In terms of the distribution of shares under the **“right-to-buy” scheme**, we were unable to find a registry/database showing how many *different* residents of municipalities have purchased shares in a wind project (given that one resident can purchase up to 50 shares). It was only possible to see how many shares have been purchased in total. If many different residents bought shares, this would indicate that the pricing of the shares is affordable for a good number of local residents: on the other hand, if a fewer number of residents purchased many shares each, this would indicate that there is a small number of wealthy residents who are able to benefit financially from wind projects like the cases explored above, whereas this is not feasible for a majority of the surrounding community.

Another limitation is the fact that we had to translate many of our sources from Danish to English. There is definitely the possibility that some nuances were lost in this process, and that some documents and texts were partially mistranslated. However, given the comments and information provided by Interviewee 3, it seems that most (if not all) of the translated information we collected related to Danish energy policies and processes was correct, since their statements corroborated our existing information.

Then, the fact that we use a different definition of repowering from the one used in Denmark could have affected what kind of information we ended up analysing, and how we interpreted the results. In this sense, our assessment could be at odds with how repowering is interpreted in Denmark itself.

Finally, there is the factor that offshore wind is seen as the preferred way forward for many

in Denmark, but our report mainly focuses on onshore wind. This means it might be more difficult to convince people to reconsider giving onshore wind (specifically repowering) a chance, since public opinion seems to be less receptive towards any new projects (judging from complaints and how articles about the projects have been written). Nevertheless, it could also be that the level of local acceptance is completely dependent on the process of repowering itself and how community-based it is (judging by the success of Sdr. Bork and the comments made by Interviewee 3).

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3. ANNEX 1: BIBLIOGRAPHY

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4. ANNEX 2: INTERVIEWEES

List of interviewees (including role of interviewee, date, duration of the interview);

- Interview 1: Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S (Sep. 25, 2023; 10.00 - 11.30 AM)

- Participants:
 - Jonas Pagh Jensen – Head of Sustainability Value Chain Engagement
 - Antonios Polychronopoulos - Commercial Sales Manager (Northern Europe)
 - Maximilian Schnippering - Head of Sustainability (only organised the Interview)
- Interview 2: Expert from another OEM in Denmark
- Interview 3: Urban planner working for Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality in Denmark (held online on 22nd November 2023; 9:00 - 10:00 AM)

5. ANNEX 3: INTERVIEWS

3.1. Interview with experts from Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S as part of WP3.

As part of the [JustWind4All](#) EU project, an interview was conducted with experts from one of the most renowned OEMs, Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S (SGRE). The interview was organised by Aarhus University Prof. George Xydis with the Head of Sustainability, Maximilian Schnippering, the Head of Sustainability Value Chain Engagement, Jonas Pagh Jensen, and the Commercial Sales Manager (Northern Europe), Antonios Polychronopoulos. Both Jonas and Antonios very actively participated in the interview. George's questions are listed below as a point of departure for the discussion and the most important points are summarised below each question.

1. *What are the current challenges and implications of ageing – and unavoidably underperforming – wind turbines in the Danish case, and how are stakeholders addressing issues such as maintenance, performance decline, and potential decommissioning? In what way are local communities affected by the decommissioning of wind turbines? Where do the old blades end up?*

The challenges and implications of ageing, according to Jonas, weigh the owners and not the OEMs. Even though they provide service and maintenance to the customers, the end-of-life cycle of the wind turbines is out of scope since the decision lies with the customer.

Turbines typically come with a technical certification for a certain number of years, and scheduled maintenance in order to secure their smooth operation. The critical part of old turbines is the spare parts. Due to low volume, the cost might not be viable for the operation of the wind turbine (WT). Addressing that issue, new turbines have been built based on modularization according to Antonios since it's more flexible and low-cost.

When historical data are examined, it becomes clear that decommissioning occurs less frequently than anticipated. The high prices of electricity might be the reason behind it, according to both Jonas and Antonios. Furthermore, it has been noticed that the lifetime of the WTs is prolonged by a decade in many many cases. So, usually, the decommissioning takes place only when the cost of operation and maintenance exceeds the energy production gains. Moreover, it has been pointed out that decommissioning wind turbines now involves route surveys, which have become more complex due to new policies and regulations. This can affect local communities and require additional permits. Those route surveys might be costly, but they can create more job opportunities due to the manpower that is required, which can be positive for the local community.

An alternative to decommissioning is repowering, meaning some of the components of an existing WT could be upgraded. That way new technologies can be implemented. Cases of repowering though have as a result the early retirement of the WT, in order to replace the 1 MW turbines with a 4 MW or a 5 MW wind turbine. In conclusion, everything depends on the owner's decision and how economically viable each choice can be. It is predicted by the interviewees that in case the energy prices go down, many owners might prefer decommissioning instead of repowering.

2. What are the current practices and challenges associated with the recycling of existing wind turbines?

After the decommissioning there are 2 paths. The first is where wind farms get a second life, either by repowering or taking them down and restructuring them according to height regulations. Common places where that occurred were North Italy, Ireland, and the UK. The second path is where the WTs do not gain a second life. Wind turbines contain multiple metal components, which are categorised into different groups. The revenue generated from selling these metals to local scrap dealers contributes to supporting local metal recycling initiatives. The most important aspect of decommissioning is the non-metallic parts since there are no established recycling techniques.

In SGRE, according to Jonas, they have been working on building an overview of recycling opportunities for wind turbines in each country. This suggests that they are actively exploring solutions for recycling composite materials. In terms of recycling blades, they are often used in the making of cement, where they are broken down and processed further. Thus, the resin is converted into a fuel, which is the highest level of energy recovery rather than recycling, and fibres will essentially take the role of sand in the manufacturing process.

Recycling capabilities and practices vary significantly between countries, with notable differences in Europe. Some countries are more advanced in recycling wind turbine blades than others. Current recycling methods include mechanical and, to some extent, chemical processes. However, challenges exist in breaking down and separating composite materials efficiently. Researchers and the industry are currently investigating new cutting-edge recycling techniques, such as thermal or chemical treatment methods. Although theoretically possible, these technologies are currently not commercially viable due to significant expenses. The following phase is to establish value chains to reduce the price of recycling solutions and increase their economic attractiveness for the sector. The interviewee notes that thermal or chemical treatment methods can cost over seven euros per kilogram, which is significantly higher than the cost of new composite materials. Therefore, achieving cost-effectiveness is a challenge in recycling wind turbine blades.

The need to find a balance between the costs and benefits of recycling wind turbine blades is brought up from the standpoint of procurement. The whole supply chain must adjust since recycling will change how raw materials are provided. Suppliers will have to either offer recycling technologies or come up with new business models. Business models and the general business climate will also be impacted by this technical advancement in recycling. In order to deal with these changes and prevent any potential negative societal repercussions, the interviewee emphasises the necessity for proactive actions across the supply chain.

3. *Are there any governance bottlenecks or best practices? Are there sufficient policies in place to manage successful operation & maintenance and decommissioning or circular principles?*

Jonas mentioned the IEC 61400-28-2 technical standard, which is a standard created for recycling wind turbines. To define best practices for the recycling process, this standard is presently being developed and SGRE is working on implementing it. Despite media attention to the subject, Jonas recognizes that there hasn't been much decommissioned wind turbine material produced, and there hasn't been much practice with standardised, industrialised decommissioning procedures. The sector is currently attempting to build recycling processes and overcome these issues, emphasising the importance of governance in establishing recycling standards.

Commenting especially on how to recycle wind turbines, the interviewees address the lack of legally required criteria in the wind energy sector. They point out that the size and kind of consumers involved frequently determine how recycling methods are received. Due to their substantial investments, larger customers may proactively embrace best practices without government regulations.

4. *Is the goal for more circular forms of wind energy an outward goal or more internally formed (does it originate from the company)?*

The choices surrounding recycling and sustainability policies are not made by manufacturers; rather, they are a response to consumer preferences and governmental requirements. A policy cannot be enforced on customers if it is not required by law.

The interviewees point out that while they work to create wind turbines in the most environmentally friendly manner possible, they also have to take the demands of their customers and the industry's competitors into account. They provide both conventional and recyclable wind turbine blades, the latter of which is an optional extra that has a price. Overall, cost factors and customer preferences are frequently important factors in the decision-making.

5. *In light of proposed sanctions on Critical Raw Materials (CRM) by China on the Chip sector, and the Critical Raw Materials Act of the EU, are there sufficient forms of governance to maintain the security of materials for wind turbine production? If not, where do these need to be addressed and how? How would policy/governance help in formulating circular policies with regard to the security of supply?*

Jonas expressed concerns regarding the mining of Rare Earth Elements (REE) and the production of magnets outside the EU but it is an issue that cannot be addressed by a single company. Europe has not necessarily pursued a policy of self-producing REEs. They recognize that developing a supply chain that complies with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards can present both possibilities and problems when it comes to environmental permits. Antonios emphasises the intricacy of the problem and the need to come up with a self-production plan.

6. *To what extent does pausing an established and effective scheme (Open Door Scheme) create investment uncertainty, and what are the potential consequences and strategies to mitigate such uncertainty? Did the new Marine Plan play a role? How about the*

increased number of designated nature and environmental protection zones – Did that play a role? Do you foresee that a lot more projects will be put on hold? And how the company plans to deal with it?

The interviewees underline the necessity of certainty and assured volumes in the wind energy sector, both from the standpoint of an investor and the supply chain. They emphasise the need for consistent and firm volumes that can provide a return on investment in order to achieve the necessary capital expenditure (CAPEX) for wind energy projects to satisfy goals like those set forth in the Paris Agreement. Moreover, the interviewees emphasise the need to have clear laws for the sector since ambiguous standards might result in retroactive judgments that delay projects due to a recent maritime plan that defines Natura zones and might have an impact on offshore wind production. Moreover, it is discussed how these uncertainties might influence investment choices, raise risk, and make it more difficult to get investments. It is also pointed out that these issues have repercussions for initiatives in the future as well as for present ones. Antonios highlights that because they are large suppliers, many regulatory concerns are not directly within their control. They do, however, take part in industry networks and conversations about difficulties with obtaining permits. The problems in obtaining permits may also raise project risks and financial issues, affecting not just ongoing projects but also potential future investments. It is also emphasised that independent power providers like Vattenfall and Orsted deal with comparable difficulties, and that these problems might have an impact on the whole supply chain.

7. German TSO last year paid more than EUR 70 million to downwardly regulate Danish power generation. Do you foresee this growing? What will be the impact on the Governance & in developing huge inequalities? Do you think this will have an impact on the O&M's activities? In what way?

Jonas states that it is necessary to reconsider energy policies as a result of greater rates of renewable energy penetration. They advocate a move toward more regional or circular practices that make use of localised renewable energy generation. The interviewees admit that, while they may not have detailed knowledge of the circumstances, they have seen that, since Denmark has installed a sizable amount of renewable energy capacity, there is frequently more energy output than consumption. In addition, it is mentioned how critical it is to develop new energy consumption habits or to use energy more efficiently locally, particularly in light of the expansion of offshore wind power. The creation of energy islands and the requirement for more energy transmission to other nations has been discussed. They also take into account the difficulty of raising power usage, for example, through the use of electric cars or other methods.

In summary, it highlighted the need to adapt energy strategies and consumption patterns to accommodate higher levels of renewable energy production, including offshore wind capacity and energy islands.

“The views reflect the view of the interviewed persons and not SGRE’s”

3.2. Interview with an expert from another OEM in Denmark as part of WP3

As part of the JustWind4All EU project, an interview was conducted with experts from another OEM in Denmark, who want to maintain their anonymity. The interview was

organised by Aarhus University Prof. George Xydis. His questions are listed below as a point of departure for the discussion and the most important points are summarised below each question.

1. What are the current challenges and implications of ageing – and unavoidably underperforming – wind turbines in the Danish case, and how are stakeholders addressing issues such as maintenance, performance decline, and potential decommissioning? In what way are local communities affected by the decommissioning of wind turbines? Where do the old blades end up?

According to the expert, the challenges and consequences of ageing primarily burden the owners of wind turbines, rather than the original wind turbine manufacturers. Despite the fact that OEMs offer services and long-term maintenance plans to their customers – and our company offers one of the longest service contracts in the market – the end-of-life cycle of wind turbines falls under the customer's jurisdiction. It is always a matter of the viability of the market, existing supply chain conditions in general and so many other things such as, for instance, if a 20-year old wind farm is competitive enough compared to today's conditions. Today wind turbines are produced in a way to require minimum maintenance, which 20-25 years ago was not used.

Regarding decommissioning – and based on the above – we don't hear that very often (at least until now). It occurs less frequently than originally anticipated. This is an indication that despite all the challenges with the old wind turbines, the owners decide that the life of the wind turbines can be prolonged. This means that either the costs for decommissioning (ABEX) are extremely high and perhaps have not initially been calculated when the permits were obtained, or they might be thinking of repowering as an option. Decommissioning is a very complicated process – a new study on its own subject to different policies and regulations which could impact local communities and necessitate additional permits.

Since repowering was mentioned, it is true that the definition varies in different countries. It involves upgrading some components of existing wind turbines to incorporate new technologies or replacement of old wind turbines with new for more powerful e.g., 6-7 MW each to the exact same spot – and this creates some misalignments in the industry. It is definitely linked to the owner's financial stability and willingness to invest further in the industry.

2. What are the current practices and challenges associated with the recycling of existing wind turbines?

As industry in general, we are at a point where decisions need to be taken. You cannot extend the lifetime of the wind turbine for a decade – this is common – just because the decommissioning costs are high. After decommissioning, since the turbines contain various metal components, these are categorised into different groups. The revenue generated from selling these metals to local scrap dealers contributes to supporting local metal recycling initiatives. However, the most challenging aspect of decommissioning lies in the non-metallic parts, as effective recycling techniques for these components are needed – and will be more needed in the future.

Within our company, we have unveiled circularity solutions to end landfill for the blades. A recently unearthed chemical process can demonstrate that epoxy-based turbine blades, whether in active use or deposited in landfills, can be transformed into a viable source of raw material, potentially enabling the construction of new turbine blades. So, in a way, that's revolutionary since it focuses also on the old ones – not on the ones that are produced today.

3. Are there any governance bottlenecks or best practices? Are there sufficient policies in place to manage successful operation & maintenance and decommissioning or circular principles?

Despite the media attention focused on this issue, the interview expert acknowledges that there has been a limited production of decommissioned wind turbine materials, and standardised, industrialised decommissioning procedures are still relatively scarce. The industry is presently focused on creating recycling processes – based on the German standard DIN SPEC 4866 and the under development pan-European standard - addressing these challenges, pointing out the significance of governance in establishing recycling standards, in general.

4. Is the goal for more circular forms of wind energy an outward goal or more internally formed (does it originate from the company)?

The interviewee emphasised that while they strive to manufacture wind turbines in an environmentally responsible manner, they must also consider the demands of their customers and competitors within the industry. This is what mainly drives the decisions. They can now offer an above 80% recyclable wind turbine blade if requested, and the company works towards a zero waste goal for wind turbines until 2040. The decisions regarding recycling and sustainability policies are not driven by manufacturers per se; instead, they are shaped by consumer choices and government mandates. It should be stressed however, that a policy cannot be imposed on customers unless it is legally mandated.

5. In light of proposed sanctions on Critical Raw Materials (CRM) by China on the Chip sector, and the Critical Raw Materials Act of the EU, are there sufficient forms of governance to maintain the security of materials for wind turbine production? If not, where do these need to be addressed and how? How would policy/governance help in formulating circular policies with regard to the security of supply?

The interviewee raised concerns about the extraction of Rare Earth Elements (REE) and magnet production outside the EU. He emphasised that this is a complex issue that cannot be resolved by a single company. Europe has not necessarily pursued a policy of self-sufficiency in REE production. They recognize that establishing a supply chain that aligns with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards can present both opportunities and challenges, particularly in terms of obtaining environmental permits. There is clearly a necessity of devising a unified continent-centred strategy.

6. To what extent does pausing an established and effective scheme (Open Door Scheme) create investment uncertainty, and what are the potential consequences and strategies to mitigate such uncertainty? Did the new Marine Plan play a role? How about the increased number of designated nature and environmental protection zones – Did that play a role? Do you foresee that a lot more projects will be put on hold? And how the company plans to deal with it?

The interviewee underscored the need for well-defined regulations within the sector, as vague standards could lead to retroactive judgments, causing delays in an already obstructed supply chain, in several future projects. A characteristic example is the recent maritime plan that designates Natura zones, which impacts offshore wind production. It was pointed out that sometimes major suppliers have regulatory issues that go beyond their direct control. Delays in obtaining permits can heighten project risks and financial concerns in general. This

indeed, creates some concerns in the market, especially when it comes to future investments.

7. German TSO last year paid more than EUR 70 million to downwardly regulate Danish power generation. Do you foresee this growing? What will be the impact on the Governance & in developing huge inequalities? Do you think this will have an impact on the O&M's activities? In what way?

The interviewee suggests a re-evaluation of such humongous energy projects. He proposes a shift towards regional and circular practices that leverage localised renewable energy generation. Huge projects have a more international character and decisions should be carefully taken. Expanding the offshore wind power sector is not a panacea, however, it generates wealth and secures Europe further. This goes along with the need for increased energy transmission to other countries and along with the challenges of boosting energy usage, such as through the adoption of electric vehicles or other methods. Projecting whether such a pattern will grow in the near future is solely related to responsible consumption – and the general population is not there yet – and with adapting energy strategies that can accommodate the growing levels of renewable energy production, in general.

3.3 Interview with an Urban Planner from Ringkøbing-Skjern Municipality

Triangulation - we were able to confirm the information about the wind planning procedure and the different laws/incentives in place by asking the urban planner; her answers helped to reinforce/doubly confirm the information we had already found in our document review (this also confirms that the information we translated was translated well).

The wind turbine **developer** plays a key/vital role in perceptions of a wind project (more than we originally thought) – they are encouraged by local politicians to engage with residents, ask their opinions, and consult them about the possibility of creating a wind project before they even hand in an application. This part of the process is seen as incredibly important: without this, projects become contentious, because local residents cannot see their “**place**”, or cannot see themselves in the project. The **local value** of a wind project has to be made clear to people/has to be visible; without it, people complain – especially environmental complaints can have a powerful effect, in either delaying a project significantly or halting it completely.

Essentially, she stated that almost everything regarding the success of a project depends on the developer, and the interactions they have with neighbours and local residents – for Sdr. Bork, there were positive interactions with the developer (also due to them being locally based). For Sdr. Bork, the developer being local landowners definitely helped perceptions of the project – existing closeness to residents helped people to **see themselves** in the project, and the fact that it was initiated by people close to home/in a collaborative way ... there was an inauguration that 200 members of the local community attended, and they were all very happy. Most disagreements came from people in the neighbouring Varde Municipality, and the municipalities (while collaborating to find a solution) actually went against national law to divide up the Green Pool and ensure that Varde could also benefit from the money (they discovered this afterwards – and the national law has since been changed to accommodate this).

There are two sides to the issue – on the one hand, there is the climate crisis, and the perception of the city council of RS is that as a municipality, they have the space, land, and wind resources to deliver renewable energy projects, “it is in our DNA”. Therefore, there is a certain responsibility to act and make use of these conditions. On the other hand, there are neighbours and local societies that are negatively affected (like, “they think that their view is ruined”), so it is important to find a balance between the two. The process/point of agreement can sometimes be difficult: need to ensure that local people also feel like they can deliver/find their interest in the green process and the efforts made towards implementing green energy.

Laws/legislation have gotten “sharper” – the RS Municipality takes great care to ensure that all environmental impact assessments are conducted incredibly thoroughly; they are scared that it ever becomes a problem, or that people complain at any point about any environmental factors/animal species being affected. RS has not had any issues/problems with environmental complaints, but also because they put a lot of effort into avoiding this. A national interest in putting test turbines in certain areas (which they saw as an opportunity through the Sdr. Bork project) also delayed the process somewhat.

In terms of local perceptions and resistance, it appears that the closest neighbours in the immediate vicinity of the turbines generally experience all of the negative effects/burdens of wind projects, but the local community as a whole/beyond that does benefit from it. There is the money from the Green Pool which can be used for green projects in the area, as well as the shares in the wind park, and the developer pays some yearly fixed amount to the residents as well (the interviewee was not sure about this exactly and couldn’t confirm fully: she knew of the practice, but this is generally handled by the developer and does not involve the municipality at all).

The future – the municipality is looking towards multipurpose energy systems, which could involve efforts like combining forest planting with a solar panel farm; mixed use energy systems seen as a possibility for the future, and the RS Municipality is encouraging applications for this until 1 March 2024 (has not been put into practice yet). Some people see the benefit of this approach, others do not – often the success of a project is more likely if it is done in a location where this type of energy production exists already, with wind turbines especially. This makes repowering, or expanding existing wind farms, the most effective strategy for increasing onshore wind energy production/capacity.

Improvements to the system? – The urban planner is of the opinion that, if you find the right area and take the neighbourhood into consideration and talk to the local society, then it’s not difficult to do wind planning – but you have to find the right community and the right place to do it. Then, it is not important how long exactly the process takes, as long as you do it in the right way (which is consulting extensively with the community impacted by the development).